

**Perception and Attitude of Third and Fourth Year Pharmacy Students
towards Traditional and Virtual Laboratories**

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⁴Undergraduate Thesis

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June 2022

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The traditional laboratory has been defined as a room expressly constructed for the demonstration of on-the-spot practical experiments by a facilitator. Meanwhile, the virtual laboratory synchronous sessions, which use either Zoom or Google Meet, include a discussion of pre-laboratory and post-laboratory lectures.

Methodology. The participants are composed of B.S. Pharmacy students (n=173) in Valenzuela City, were selected using a simple random sampling technique, specifically through a computer-generated random list. A survey questionnaire given online was used to collect data, and data was then summarized and tabulated using Microsoft Excel and were analyzed using different statistical methods such as the paired t-test to answer the research questions in the study.

Results. The results showed that there is a difference between traditional and virtual laboratories in terms of effectiveness, convenience, perception, and attitude. It is shown that "*Effectiveness*" "*Convenience*" and "*Perception and attitude*" have p-values of less than 0.05 ($p = <0.001$), implying that the results are all significant.

Conclusion. Given this situation, the majority of the students agreed that traditional and virtual laboratories differ when it comes to their effectiveness and convenience. Hence, the perception and attitude of pharmacy students towards traditional and virtual laboratories also differ, implying that traditional setting is more favorable for them.

Keywords: *Traditional laboratory, Virtual laboratory, Effectiveness, Convenience*

1.0 Introduction

This chapter states the background, problem, hypothesis, purpose, significance as well as scope and limitations of the study.

1.1. Background of the study

In December 2019, a new virus has been discovered as it infected thousands of people in Wuhan China. This infection, now called COVID-19 caused by Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-COV-2), rapidly spread in the said country and eventually in the world, leading to a global pandemic. The said disease affects the respiratory system of a patient manifesting as cough to severe pneumonia. Although as compared to the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-COV), the probability of a patient dying in SARS-COV 2 is lower than MERS-COV, however, the SARS-COV 2 affected more life than MERS-COV since it is highly transmissible (Shi et. al., 2020). Due to this, countries around the world implemented preventive measures to combat the virus including regular sanitation, total lockdown, social distancing as well as wearing masks. Consequently, the pandemic has disrupted economic, health, and education system as well. The universities are still prohibited to conduct classes, thereby the education shifts from traditional face-to-face classes to virtual or online learning. Jena (2020) stated that, due to this spontaneous event, the universities had a short amount of time to prepare for online classes making it stressful for both students and teachers. The classes in an online set-up are deemed as flexible because it is divided into two, namely, synchronous and asynchronous session. The synchronous sessions are usually conducted to applications like Zoom, Google meets, and the likes in which teachers can discuss the lesson with students. On the other hand, asynchronous activities include offline tasks like assignments and projects needed to pass before the due date set by the teachers. The usual application used for the asynchronous session is Canvas in which students can upload their assignments as well as download modules. The online class has its benefits as people may not be able to get COVID-19 and at the same time, the delivery of education is uninterrupted. However, the effectiveness of education is affected by many factors. Jena also mentioned that through the online class, students are subjected to digital literacy, however, it is a challenge for those students with no Wi-Fi, gadgets, and a safe and conducive environment. The quality of education is at risk in a way that teachers are unable to fully assess the learnings of the students. Physical interactions are also gone which is a crucial part of the development of students. Furthermore, students' skills are also undeveloped and/or underdeveloped which may become a problem once the students graduate. Fortunately, most

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universities are offering “webinars” or online seminars to fill the gap of knowledge of their students.

Back in face-to-face classes, the universities provide seminars, on-the-job training, as well as other tasks that aim to develop the skills of the students. For instance, students in medicine and allied health courses have laboratories that are essential in preparing the students for the actual field. The traditional laboratory has been described as a room that is specially designed for the teaching of the on-hand practical experiments which will be demonstrated by a facilitator. In a traditional setting, all students carry out different tasks depending on the type of experiment they will conduct, wherein they get involved in activities such as observing, counting, measuring, experimenting, recording, and carrying out fieldwork. These activities could not be simply carried out if the laboratory is not well equipped with the resources and materials that are necessary for carrying out their task. The experiment begins by explaining the concepts, procedures, and proper handling of equipment. The students are commonly grouped together as they work collaboratively with one another. They are focusing on the key terms and functions that are written in their manual procedures, and use demonstration to better understand the concepts. Before handling the apparatus available inside the laboratory students should be knowledgeable first on the purpose of the equipment and how they should be handled which will be instructed by the facilitator. There is a person that will be assigned upon conducting the procedure to supervise the students upon handling the instruments to prevent accidents and possible errors during the experiment (Ural, 2016). Through laboratory experience, students will be able to apply what they have learned and read in their laboratory manuals thus developing their understanding of the learned concept. According to Li and Wong (2018), a traditional laboratory is believed to have an effect based on the awareness of the people, meaning, the students are more likely to have a greater chance to recall what they see in real-time than what they hear. Inquiry-based type laboratories induce the potential of students to enhance their skills and abilities to propose scientifically oriented questions, create hypotheses, design and conduct investigations, formulate and revise systematic explanations, and collaborate as well as create scientific arguments (Szalay & Toth, 2016). Laboratory activities allow students to learn and at the same time improve their ability in following procedures and further enhance their skills regarding experiments that involve observation. Moreover, this also explores their potential when students get knowledgeable in manipulating apparatuses.

To keep providing education to students during the pandemic, most university departments offered laboratory courses in which the students will also perform and observe

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laboratory works but with limitations. The virtual laboratory synchronous sessions, using either Zoom or Google meet, include a discussion of pre-laboratory and post-laboratory lectures. On the other hand, the asynchronous session includes giving tasks like worksheets, assignment, Canvas discussion board, or home-based activity that requires video presentation. The home-based activity pertains to an activity in which the student will perform experiments from their respective houses then the students will record the process and results of the experiment and submit it in a video presentation. If home-based activity is not applicable, the professor may include a video-based experiment in the worksheet in which the students will watch the video to answer the questions on the worksheets. The last option would be the Labster Simulation in which the students will conduct experiments in a game-type setting. Although it can be demanding, some researchers believed that virtual laboratories are still great during this pandemic because it is safer. In the virtual laboratory, the university will create a space where students can interact with laboratory equipment or other activity by the means of a computer interface. Virtual laboratories are capable of simulating extreme conditions and assisting students in safely conducting experiments. The absence of actual dangerous chemicals and hazardous materials keeps students away from the probable risks of laboratory accidents (Budai & Kuczmann, 2018). However, this can only be applied if the students do not perform any experiments at home. It is also necessary to take note that in the traditional laboratory, there are preventive measures and guidelines to avoid accidents. And in case of accidents, there are areas and predetermined procedures to follow with the help of the proctor. As mentioned earlier, when home-based activity is not applicable, the Labster Simulation is beneficial. Labster Simulation is software developed to perform activities regarding biology, chemistry, physics, and the like. The said simulation is presented in 3D animation in an interactive space. It also allows the controller to move and touch objects. There is an objective to be fulfilled and there are open-ended questions that assess the learning as well as critical thinking of students (<https://www.labster.com>). However, to gain access to it an individual must have a gadget that supports the software program, preferably a laptop or a desktop computer. The individual must also establish a smooth connection to the internet to access the platform, which makes it less applicable to individual work because not every student has gadgets and smooth internet service. To give a solution to this matter, the Labster Simulation is then done by a group, which turns out to be much beneficial as students are given the chance to communicate, share ideas, and explore things with their group mates. Even though the first-hand experience of the simulation cannot be experienced by every student, it is replaced by interactions of students which is a vital component of learning.

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This study aims to see the perception of the third and fourth-year Pharmacy students of a private institution in Valenzuela City regarding virtual and face-to-face laboratories. The researchers aim to compare the virtual and traditional laboratories in terms of how cost-friendly they are, how they deliver education, how they provide manual dexterity, proper technique in handling tools and equipment as well as their convenience. This study also aims to determine if the students prefer traditional laboratories or virtual laboratories.

1.2. Statement of the problem

The following research questions are formulated by the researchers to be a guide in fulfilling the stated objectives of this study. A statistical approach is used in assessing the data because this research is quantitative in nature.

1.2.1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

- a. Age
- b. Gender
- c. Year

1.2.2. How effective is virtual laboratory as compared to the traditional laboratory in terms of:

- a. Being cost-friendly
- b. Learning delivery
- c. Providing manual dexterity
- d. Providing proper techniques in handling tools and equipment

1.2.3. How convenient are virtual laboratories compared to traditional laboratories in terms of:

- a. Facilities
- b. Accessibility of devices, materials, and instruments used
- c. Getting assistance from professors
- d. Creating an output
- e. Being in a group
- f. Organizing own time

1.2.4. Is there a significant difference between the effectiveness of traditional and virtual laboratories?

1.2.5. Is there a significant difference between the convenience of traditional and virtual laboratories?

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1.2.6. Is there a significant difference in students' perception and attitude between traditional and virtual laboratories?

1.3. Hypothesis of the study

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the effectiveness of traditional and virtual laboratories.

Ha₁: There is a significant difference between the effectiveness of traditional and virtual laboratories.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the convenience of traditional and virtual laboratories.

Ha₂: There is a significant difference between the convenience of traditional and virtual laboratories.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference between third and fourth-year students' perceptions and attitudes towards traditional and virtual laboratories.

Ha₃: There is a significant difference between third and fourth-year students' perceptions and attitudes towards traditional and virtual laboratories.

1.4. Significance of the study

This study determines the perceptions and attitudes of 3rd Year and 4th Year BS Pharmacy students about the virtual and traditional laboratory, which may serve as a basis for understanding the effects of the newly implemented virtual laboratory activities. Furthermore, the results of this study may be proven to be highly significant and beneficial to the following:

College of Pharmacy. This study may be helpful for the College of Pharmacy as it will help them understand the perception and attitudes of pharmacy students towards the virtual and traditional setup. This will open opportunities for the attainment of better quality education and can be used as a basis for future decision-making about the implementation of suitable and effective laboratory activities for all students.

Pharmacy students. This study may be useful for pharmacy students as it encourages them to share their perceptions and voice out their thoughts concerning their experiences with distance learning and traditional setup. The preferences gathered by the researchers will help the COP identify their next best action for a better learning environment for the pharmacy students.

Community. This study may be beneficial to the community as it will reflect the true condition of the students during the pandemic. Thereby, this research will be an eye-opener because it may expose the community to the struggles faced by the students during traditional or virtual laboratories. Once the community learned about the lack of skills during the pandemic, they may provide training, seminars, or programs that can improve the skills of future pharmacists. Exposure to actual practice areas is needed for the students to gain skills, thereby, municipalities or even barangays may launch a program in which they will coordinate with pharmaceutical companies in their vicinity to give proper and free training to pharmacy students.

Future Researchers. The study will be significant for future researchers as it may serve as a guide for them to further scrutinize the perceptions and attitudes of students and they may also include other variables regarding the experiences and other factors encountered in both learning set up. In addition, this may also help future researchers to find a solution to the current problems experienced by the students for the attainment and improvement of education. They may also use this research as source material in supporting their topic.

1.5. Scope and Limitation

The study covers the perception of the third-year and fourth-year pharmacy students regarding traditional and virtual laboratories. This research focuses on the students from a private, non-sectarian educational institution located in Barangay Marulas, Valenzuela City. The participants included in this study are 3rd and 4th year pharmacy students because they experienced both traditional and virtual laboratories. They should also be currently enrolled in School Year 2021-2022 under the Pharmacy program and also taking up courses with virtual laboratories in the said university. Gender and age, on the other hand, have no restrictions. All genders and ages are encouraged to participate in this study. The status also has no restrictions, thus, regular and irregular 3rd and 4th year students can participate in this study.

On the other hand, individuals excluded in this study as respondents are the non-college, professors, as well as the researchers themselves. However, 1st and 2nd year pharmacy students of the said university under the School Year 2021-2022, are also excluded as they did not experience conducting laboratory experiments and discussions in a traditional setting. This study is also limited to pharmacy students thereby excluding other programs even if they are part of the health allied courses because the laboratory settings, virtual and traditional, described in this study are the ones being implemented by the College of Pharmacy in the same university.

2.0 Review of Related Literature and Studies

This chapter consists of the conceptual framework, the paradigm of the study, as well as local and foreign literature and studies connected to this research.

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1.1. Conceptual framework

Figure 2.1.1 serves as the conceptual framework for this research. The two variables to be differentiated in this research are stated as well as the factors that would affect this differentiation. The disadvantages and advantages of traditional and virtual laboratories rely on how cost-friendly are they as well as how they offer manual dexterity and proper technique to students (Alda, Boholano, & Dayagbil, 2020; Noel et. al., 2020). Other factors such as convenience and learning delivery may also affect the perception of the participants. These factors will be assessed through the given questionnaires to give the researchers an understanding of the perceptions of the respondents.

2.2 Paradigm of the Study

Figure 2.2.1. The paradigm of the study

Figure 2.2.1 presents the paradigm of the study which involves the input, process, output, and feedback of the study. The information to be introduced in the study includes the general profile of 3rd and 4th Year pharmacy students including their age, year, and gender. The process involves the creation of a survey questionnaire to be answered using a 4-point Likert Scale. The questionnaire is distributed through email or *Facebook messenger*. The data is then treated and the results are interpreted and analyzed after. As for the expected output of the study, the researchers anticipate finding out the preferences of the students in the two types of laboratories and weighing down which of the variables is more effective in facilitating learning. Lastly, the feedback that the researchers expect to receive in the study is the insights of 3rd and 4th Year Students regarding their traditional and virtual laboratory experiences.

3.0 Research Methodology

This chapter contains the research design, locale, ethics, instruments, sampling procedure, as well as the statistical treatment that the researcher will use or execute to come up with relevant data.

3.1 Research Design

This study used a descriptive quantitative approach to know and understand the perception and attitude of the 3rd and 4th year Pharmacy students regarding traditional and virtual laboratories. Thus, the researchers collected statistical data through the use of survey questionnaires and describe the data collected based on a statistical scale. Bloomfield and Fisher (2019) described the descriptive quantitative approach as a study that scrutinizes variables that affects a population, in which the researchers measure it to formulate description and interpretation systematically. This research is also non-experimental, wherein the researchers cannot control the variables being studied (Rutberg & Bouikidis, 2018). Lastly, this research used a comparative approach in which the differences between variables are highlighted.

3.2 Research Locale

This study was conducted in a private, non-sectarian educational institution located in Barangay Marulas, Valenzuela City, Metro Manila along 120 Mac Arthur Highway. It received independent status in 2009 and university-wide ISO 9001:2015 certification in 2015. It was identified as a mature teaching institution Category A(t) by CHED in 2008, and it was awarded the autonomous status in 2009. The University has six campuses, but the researchers are most interested in the Valenzuela campus, as stated earlier. The said campus was founded in 1967. Basic education, senior high school, undergraduate degree programs, and post-graduate programs are among the many programs offered by educational institutions. It is well-known for its technology-assisted teaching methods, which allow them to 'improve man as a man' by providing high-quality educational delivery. The researchers picked the said university as the laboratory courses being offered are conducted virtually, making it a great source of data for students who experienced both traditional and virtual laboratories.

3.3 Research Ethics

According to Resnik (2020), ethics in research is vital as it allows the collaboration of the participants and researchers to be fair and surrounded with respect. Furthermore, working ethically promotes the welfare of the participants since their data is exposed to the risk of a data breach. Consequently, the researchers adhere to the code of ethics by maintaining the confidentiality of the data collected from respondents. The survey questionnaire was disseminated with the participants' permission if they agree to participate in the research through the consent form. Due to the fact that this study was conducted during a pandemic crisis, the collection of data was conducted in an online setting. Any face-to-face contact with the participants is not allowed. Given the situation, the researchers used *Google forms* as compared to the traditional printed questionnaire. The platforms on which the link for the questionnaire is disseminated are *Facebook messenger* and email. These platforms will make it easier for the researchers to collect data, thus making the gathering of data more efficient. The participants are also free to contact the researchers about any concerns through the said platforms.

The researchers also recognized the participants' perceptions and attitudes about the provided topic, as well as their responses to the research instrument. In which they are free not to include their name and email address, but some information such as age, year, as well as their section, must be filled out to make sure the relativity of the study. The year and section should be given to assess whether they fall under the specific criteria set by the researchers. The researchers assure that there is no data breach as the collected data was sorted using Microsoft Excel and only the members of the group, as well as the statistician, can access the file. The excel file only contains the answers of the participants to the questionnaire and not their personal information. The researchers employed a coding manual that enhanced the protection of the respondents as their personal details are replaced with codes that are only disclosed within the group. The group also forbids any dissemination of the email address given by the respondents. Aside from data breaches, the respondents may also feel uncomfortable discussing certain matters, and for that, the researchers gave the respondents the privilege to withdraw from the study anytime. They can also refuse to answer specific questions once they do not feel like answering them, and they are not required to provide any reason for failing to reply to any question or declining to participate in the survey.

The scientific validity of data states that valid and accurate data can only be obtained from a certified sample. The researchers aim to attain honesty, integrity, and objectiveness upon

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conducting the research study. In which all the data that will be gathered is purely integrated from the respondent's perception to prevent any fabrication and plagiarism of the data to provide information that only relies on the gathered facts. Moreover, objectivity and integrity are also important to maintain consistency and avoid biased analysis upon interpreting the results. In this study the absence of underpowered and biased statements is highly encouraged; whereas everything obtained from the data is represented in the study's result.

To keep the participants informed, the researchers sent a confirmation email once the participants are done answering the questionnaire. They also got updates about the research through email or *Facebook messenger* chat, this way the participants were informed about how the study is going and how their data is being handled. Until the research is over, each of the participants will continuously receive updates about any important changes done to the research that would be of concern to them. Once the study has concluded, the researchers may send a copy of the final manuscript to each of the participants if ever they request it.

To make this all possible, the study underwent validation from Institutional Ethics Review Committee (IERC). The ethics committee is the one that assessed if the study conforms to the moral and professional standards, thereby assuring the quality, integrity, and legitimacy of the paper.

The data obtained from the participants was used for the benefit of the study. Significant changes are done to this research as it progresses which is why the data collected must be retained for a certain duration. Personal information such as the participant's age, email address, and section will be retained up until the study is over while their answers that served as the backbone of this research will be retained for another 3 years after this research is concluded. After 3 years, only the research results and the final manuscript will remain for the benefit of the University and future researchers. No information will be shared about the participants with anyone outside of the research team. The information collected from this research project will be kept private. Three years after the results have been established, all the collected information from the participants will be deleted from every platform and researcher's device. Any printed materials will be destroyed in a manner that leaves no possibility for the reconstruction of information. They will be burned, shredded, pulped, and pulverized by the researchers.

3.4 Research Instruments

To obtain the objectives of this study, the researchers used a survey form to gather the data of the participants. However, due to this pandemic, the researchers conducted the survey using *Google Forms* to reach participants at a great distance. The questionnaire used in this study went through validation by a certified psychometrician to ensure the accuracy and relevancy of the questions. The questionnaire has three parts; the first one contains the information of the respondents, such as age, gender, year, as well as their section. The second part contains the questions about traditional laboratories and the third part includes the questions about the virtual laboratory. The questionnaire is answerable by a 4-point Likert Scale in which participants will decide whether they agree, strongly agree, disagree, or strongly disagree with the given statements. The questions inside the second and third parts of the questionnaire are divided into factors affecting the effectiveness of traditional and virtual laboratories. The said factors include cost-friendly, learning delivery, providing manual dexterity and proper technique under effectiveness and facilities, accessibility of devices, materials, and instruments used, getting assistance from professors, creating an output, being in a group, as well as organizing own time under convenience. The participants will answer the questionnaire provided to them within 30 to 50 minutes since it consists of three parts. Within the estimated time, the participants will also sign the informed consent provided before part one of the questionnaire. The participants should also understand that their participation in this study should be completely voluntary, thereby, the researchers will not give any incentives after answering the questionnaire.

In order to get the attention of potential respondents, the researchers disseminated a poster. This poster consists of information about the research. It includes the purpose of this study, the criteria set by the researchers, the duration to accomplish the questionnaire, the email of the principal investigator if ever there is a concern, as well as the link and QR code that will redirect the participants to the *Google form* which contains the informed consent and the questionnaire of this study. The said poster was disseminated by the researchers through group chats on *Facebook messenger*, as well as using email. After sending the poster, the researchers will continuously entertain the potential respondents and will assist them step-by-step in accomplishing both the informed consent and questionnaire.

There could be instances where the researchers may use Google meet as well as Zoom in gathering data once requested by the respondents. Because face-to-face meetings are prohibited, the researchers can set up a meeting using Google Meet or Zoom and ask questions one by one.

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The researchers will not ask participants to turn their cameras on. Furthermore, the researchers will not record or photograph the meeting especially if they are unaware. Yet, no one except the researchers and the participant will be present in the meeting.

3.5 Sampling Procedure

The respondents needed in this specific study are students enrolled in 3rd year and 4th year B.S Pharmacy. Using Slovin's method, the researchers calculated the sample size of 173 3rd and 4th year students based on the population. The researchers obtained the ideal sample size for the study using the said formula with a margin of error of 0.05. To obtain the desired respondents, the researchers will assign a number to every participant within the population and then the sample size will be attained randomly. Therefore this research will use probability sampling or random sampling.

3.5.1 Sampling

The researchers used probability and simple random sampling. Simple random sampling is used when the entire population is accessible and the investigators have a list of all subjects in the target population. The researchers then select a random sample from this list using a lottery method or a computer-generated random list (Elfil & Negida, 2017). That means the researcher selected a subset of participants from a population randomly, therefore giving each member of the population an equal chance of being selected (Smith, 2015). To conduct simple random sampling, the researchers first identify the population they desire and then select a sample size. After selecting a sample size, the researchers listed the population and assign numbers to the units, then select random numbers and finally select a sample. In this specific research, the researchers focused on the currently enrolled 3rd and 4th year pharmacy students in a private institution in Valenzuela City as they possess the quality needed in this study. The participants should be currently enrolled in the BS Pharmacy program taking up courses with virtual laboratories. People who do not have the stated qualities are excluded in this study just like the non-college, professors, as well as the researchers themselves. The first and second-year colleges of the S.Y. 2021-2022 are also excluded as they only experience virtual laboratories and not both traditional and virtual. This study is also limited to pharmacy students, therefore, students from other courses cannot participate in this study because the laboratories described by the researchers are the ones seen in the pharmacy department.

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3.5.2 Sample Computation

The exact number of third and fourth-year students in a private institution in Valenzuela City during S.Y. 2021-2022 is 303. The researchers used this to know the ideal sample size for the study. Using Slovin's formula, the researchers acquired 173 students as their participants.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

$$n = \frac{303}{1 + (303)(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = 173$$

Where:

n = number or sample

N = total population

e = margin of error

1= constant value

3.5.3 Coding Manual

The researchers used a coding manual in this research to sort out data produced by the questionnaire. The researchers coded the questions, the participants, as well as their answers and present them in tabular form. The data shown is coded based on the codebook. This coding manual is important as it completely distinguishes the variables in the study making the readers understand easily the content of this research (Tran et. al., 2021). Furthermore, since the participants' data were coded, it will assure that no personal data or data that will lead to the identity of the participants will be exposed to the public.

3.6 Data Gathering

The researchers searched for participants that met the criteria. To do this, the researchers disseminated a poster that contains the details of the study. It is a great introduction to the study as it explains what this research is all about, the purpose of this study, as well as the criteria set by the researchers. Once the participants are determined, they are asked using either *Facebook messenger* or email if they are willing to be respondents to this research. If they agree to be part

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of this study, the researchers will proceed to conduct an online survey in which they will send the link to *Google Forms* which contains the informed consent and the main questionnaire of the study or they can scan the QR code seen in the poster given by the respondents. This QR code will redirect the participants to the *Google form* which possesses the informed consent as well as the questionnaire of the study. If ever the participants wish to have another form of data gathering, the researchers will create a meeting via Google meet or Zoom. The meeting credentials will be emailed or messaged through *Facebook messenger*. Once settled, the researchers will ask one question at a time to a participant.

The data gathering has two parts. The first part includes acquiring essential personal details of the participants, after that, they will now answer the second part of the questionnaire which includes questions about the traditional laboratory, then the third part which provides the questions for the virtual laboratory.

After that, the researchers compared the data of third and fourth-year pharmacy students. The researchers did analyze and interpreted the data using paired t-test. The data that was interpreted was presented in a tabular manner. The interpretations were used as a basis for answering the difference between the perception and attitude of third and fourth-year pharmacy students towards traditional and virtual laboratories.

3.7 Statistical Treatment

The researchers used the arithmetic mean in this study. According to Bhandari (2020), the mean is the most widely used measure of central tendency which includes all the values in the calculation. The mean or the average is obtained by getting the total or the sum of the values and dividing that sum by the total number of values. Because it needs equal spacing among adjacent values or scores in the scale, the mean can only be employed on interval and ratio levels of measurement.

$$X = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

Where:

X= mean

$\sum x$ = summation of all values

N= number of values

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Frequency is also involved in this study. The frequency pertains to the number of times a particular score appears in a given set of data, for instance, the number of males and females in a given sample (Glen, 2021). Furthermore, a frequency distribution is a statistical tool that visualizes the distribution of observations within a test. Frequency distribution is frequently used by analysts to depict or interpret the data obtained in a sample. It helps the researcher to quickly scan over all of the data. It indicates whether the number of observations is great or small, as well as whether they are concentrated in one location or dispersed across the entire scale (Young, 2020). In addition, the frequency of every potential value of a variable may be summarized in numbers or percentages in tables or graphs (Bhandari, 2020).

$$\% = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

Where:

%= percentage

f= frequency

N= number of values

Meanwhile, for the researchers to answer the stated problems as well as to know if there is a difference between the variables, they used paired t-test. Since this study aims to compare the perception and attitude of pharmacy students between traditional and virtual laboratories, a t-test will be advantageous. According to Hayes (2021), a t-test is an inferential statistic that is used to see if there is a substantial distinction between two groups that are related in some way. A t-test is a hypothesis-testing technique that can be used to assess an assumption that applies to a population. It also compares the average values of two data sets to see if they are from the same group.

4.0 Results

This chapter presents the results as well as findings gathered from the respondents using the survey questionnaire. All the data shown in this chapter are presented in a tabular manner. The findings presented will answer the research questions stated by the researchers. This chapter also consists of the data analysis which includes correlation and frequency.

4.1 Demographic of the Respondents

Table 4.1.1 Frequency and Percentage of Respondents regarding their Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
20 years old	25	14.5
21 years old	76	43.9
22 years old	64	37.0
23 years old	5	2.9
24 years old	1	0.6
26 years old	1	0.6
38 years old	1	0.6
Total	173	100

Table 4.1.1 above, shows the frequency as well as a percentage distribution of the respondents based on their age. It is shown that 43.9% (76) of the respondents are 21 years old, 37.0% (64) are 22 years old, 14.5% (25) are 20 years old, and 2.9% (5) are 23 years old. Meanwhile, the respondents who are 24 years old, 26 years old, as well as 38 years old are all 0.6% (1).

Table 4.1.2 Frequency and Percentage of Respondents Regarding Their Year Level

Year level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
3 rd Year	102	59
4 th Year	71	41
Total	173	100

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Table 4.1.2 above, shows the frequency as well as a percentage distribution of the respondents based on their year level. It is shown that 59% (102) of the respondents are 3rd year students while 41% (71) of the respondents are 4th year students.

Table 4.1.3 Frequency and Percentage of Respondents Regarding Their Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	38	22
Female	135	78
Total	173	100

Table 4.1.3 above, shows the frequency as well as a percentage distribution of the respondents based on their gender. It is shown that 78% (135) of the respondents are female and 22% (38) are male.

4.2 Effectiveness of Virtual Laboratory Compared to Traditional Laboratory

Table 4.2.1 Effectiveness in terms of Being Cost-friendly

Statements	Virtual Laboratory		Traditional Laboratory	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Less money is spent on buying PPEs (e.g. gloves, hairnet, and mask). (<i>Mas kaunti ang nagagastos sa pagbili ng mga PPE (hal. gloves, hairnet, and mask.)</i>)	3.28	Agree	2.06	Disagree
2. Less money is spent on buying materials (e.g. test tube, white mantle, glass slide, etc.). (<i>Mas kakaunti ang nagagastos sa pagbili ng mga materyales (hal. test tube, white mantle, glass slide, atbp.)</i>)	3.17	Agree	2.13	Disagree
3. Less money is spent on acquiring printed handouts and books required. (<i>Mas kakaunti ang nagagastos sa pagbili ng mga kinakailangang printed handouts at libro.)</i>)	3.07	Agree	1.92	Disagree
4. Worth the fee based on the services given. (<i>Sulit ang bayad base sa serbisyonang natatanggap.</i>)	2.16	Disagree	3.49	Agree
5. The cost of materials can be easily shared with groupmates. (<i>Higit na madali ang paghahati ng mga gastusin sa mga kagrupa.</i>)	2.47	Disagree	3.44	Agree
6. There is no need to spend money on public transport. (<i>Hindi na kailangan gumastos para sa transportasyon.</i>)	3.29	Agree	1.79	Disagree
7. There is no need to spend money on snacks. (<i>Hindi na kailangan gumastos para sa baon o meryenda.</i>)	3.00	Agree	1.77	Disagree
8. It is easier to save more money by not having the risk of breaking any apparatus. (<i>Mas nakakatipid ng pera sa panamagitan ng hindi pagkakaroon ng panganib na masira ang anumang kagamitan.</i>)	3.29	Agree	2.34	Disagree
9. Less money will be utilized for acquiring chemicals since it is readily available in the said area. (<i>Mas nakakatipid ng pera sa mga kemikal sapagkat matatagpuan na mismo ito sa laboratoryo.</i>)	2.66	Agree	3.23	Agree
10. There is no need to purchase a laboratory module. (<i>Hindi na kailangang bumili pa ng laboratory module.</i>)	3.22	Agree	1.78	Disagree
11. There is no need to pay a locker fee for the storage of laboratory materials. (<i>Hindi na kailangang magbayad para sa locker na nagsisilbing taguan ng mga kagamitang panglaboratoryo.</i>)	3.51	Strongly Agree	2.47	Disagree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.01	Agree	2.40	Disagree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.50)", "Disagree (1.51-2.50)", "Agree (2.51-3.50)", "Strongly Agree (3.51-4.50)"

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Table 4.2.1 above shows that the virtual laboratory gained 8 agree, 2 disagree, and 1 strongly agree while the traditional laboratory gained 8 disagree, and 3 agree. The majority of the statements are in favor of the virtual laboratory as reflected in its overall weighted mean of 3.01 which interprets as “Agree”, as compared to the traditional laboratory which acquires an overall weighted mean of 2.40 which signifies “Disagree”. The highest weighted mean that the virtual laboratory got is 3.51 which indicates “Strongly Agree” when it comes to not needing to pay a locker fee while its lowest weighted mean is 2.16 which interprets as “Disagree” when it comes to the worth of the fee based on services given. On the other hand, the traditional laboratory got 3.49 as its highest weighted mean which interprets as “Agree” when it comes to being worthy of the fee based on the services given, while its lowest weighted mean is 1.77 which indicates “Disagree” when it comes to not needing to spend money on snacks. As the result above implies, generally, respondents think that the virtual laboratory is more cost-friendly as compared to the traditional laboratory. However, the results also show that even though students use more money in the traditional laboratory set-up, the expenses are worth the fee.

Table 4.2.2 Effectiveness in terms of Learning Delivery

Statements	Virtual Laboratory		Traditional Laboratory	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Provides better learning modes (individual and group activities like an essay, research, etc.). <i>(Nakakapagbigay ng mas mahusay na mga learning modes (indibidwal at pangkatang gawain tulad ng sanaysay, pananaliksik, atbp.))</i>	2.31	Disagree	3.63	Strongly Agree
2. Lessons are being understood easier. <i>(Mas nauunawaang mabuti ang mga aralin.)</i>	2.34	Disagree	3.59	Strongly Agree
3. Scientific concepts are better explained with the help of demonstration from professors. <i>(Mas naipaliwanag ang mga konseptomong pang-aham dahil ito ay naisasagawa ng mga propesor sa harapan ng mga estudyante.)</i>	2.27	Disagree	3.66	Strongly Agree
4. Instructions and procedures are better explained. <i>(Mas naipaliwanag nang mabuti ang mga panuto at proseso.)</i>	2.24	Disagree	3.60	Strongly Agree
5. Proper disposal of waste material (e.g. carcasses, organic and inorganic chemicals, and syringes, etc.) is easily learned. <i>(Mas madaling natutunan ang tamang pagtatapon ng mga basura (hal. carcasses, organic and inorganic chemicals, and syringes atbp.))</i>	2.24	Disagree	3.60	Strongly Agree
6. There is better visualization on learning chemical reactions because of first-hand experience in conducting experiments. <i>(Mas natutunan nang maayos ang mga chemical reactions dahil mismong nararanasan ang pagsasagawa ng mga gawaing patungkol dito.)</i>	2.13	Disagree	3.68	Strongly Agree
7. The library can be used as a study area. <i>(Magagamit ang silid-aklatan upang makapag-aral.)</i>	1.98	Disagree	3.64	Strongly Agree
8. It is easier to ask the teachers and friends to better explain the concepts that are difficult to understand. <i>(Mas madaling natatanton ang mga guro at kaibigan tungkol sa mga konseptomong mahirap unawain.)</i>	2.13	Disagree	3.64	Strongly Agree
9. It is easier to concentrate. <i>(Mas madaling makapag-focus nang mabuti.)</i>	2.11	Disagree	3.58	Strongly Agree
10. After completing laboratory assignments, it is easy to listen to lectures and answer the exams. <i>(Pagkatapos makumpleto ang mga takdang-aralin ay mas napapadali ang pakikinig sa lecture at pagsagot sa pagsusulit.)</i>	2.34	Disagree	3.40	Agree
11. It is easier to understand the purpose of the lab experiment. <i>(Mas madaling maunawaan ang layunin ng eksperimentong panglaboratoryo.)</i>	2.25	Disagree	3.58	Strongly Agree
12. Learning is easier due to the simulations. <i>(Mas higit na natutunan ang mga aralin dahil sa mga simulations.)</i>	2.30	Disagree	3.46	Agree
13. It is easier to improve practical laboratory skills. <i>(Mas nahahasa ang praktikal na kasanayan sa laboratoryo.)</i>	1.96	Disagree	3.68	Strongly Agree
14. It is easier to familiarize with theories. <i>(Mas madaling natutunan ang mga teorya.)</i>	2.21	Disagree	3.50	Agree
15. Experiments are performed fast and accurately at the same time. <i>(Mas naisasagawa nang mabilis at wasto ang mga gawain.)</i>	2.27	Disagree	3.64	Strongly Agree
16. It is easier to grasp how to experiment. <i>(Mas nauunawaan kung paano gawin ang eksperimento.)</i>	2.10	Disagree	3.47	Agree
17. Handling of equipment can be done independently. <i>(Ang paggamit ng mga kagamitan ay naisasagawa ng mag-isa.)</i>	2.29	Disagree	3.34	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.20	Disagree	3.57	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.50)", "Disagree (1.51-2.50)", "Agree (2.51-3.50)", "Strongly Agree (3.51-4.50)"

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Table 4.2.2 above shows that the virtual laboratory acquired disagrees with all of the statements presented while the traditional laboratory gained 12 strongly agree, and 5 agree. The majority of the statements are in favor of the traditional laboratory as seen in its overall weighted mean of 3.57 which signifies “Strongly Agree”, as compared to the virtual laboratory which gained 2.20 which means “Disagree”. The highest weighted mean that the virtual laboratory received is 2.34 which implies “Disagree” when it comes to understanding the lesson easily, as well as listening to lectures and answering exams is much easier after completing the tasks in the said laboratory set-up, while its lowest weighted mean is 1.98 which interprets as “Disagree” when it comes to the library being a study area in this set-up. On the other hand, the traditional laboratory gained 3.68 which means “Strongly Agree”, as its highest weighted mean in two statements, particularly when visualizing the chemical reactions due to the first-hand experience in this set-up as well as improving practical laboratory skills, while its lowest weighted mean is 3.34 which signifies “Agree” when it comes to the students being able to handle equipment independently. As the results imply, the majority of the respondents think that the traditional laboratory has better learning delivery as compared to the virtual laboratory.

Table 4.2.3 Effectiveness in terms of Providing Manual Dexterity

Statements	Virtual Laboratory		Traditional Laboratory	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. It is easier to learn procedures that need eye and hand coordination. (<i>Mas madaling natututunan ang mga gawain na nangangailangan ng koordinasyon ng mata at kamay.</i>)	2.02	Disagree	3.62	Strongly Agree
2. It is easier to perform skills that need eye and hand coordination like trituration and titration. (<i>Mas madaling naisasagawa ang mga gawaing nangangailangan ng koordinasyon ng mata at kamaygaya ng trituration at titration.</i>)	2.01	Disagree	3.63	Strongly Agree
3. Tasks like trituration and titration are performed with confidence. (<i>Ang mga gawain gaya ng trituration at titration ay naisasagawa ng may kumpiyansa.</i>)	1.99	Disagree	3.52	Strongly Agree
4. It is easier to demonstrate skill during experiments. (<i>Mas madaling naipapakita ang kasanayan sa pag-eksperimento.</i>)	1.98	Disagree	3.60	Strongly Agree
5. Small quantities of chemicals can be easily measured precisely. (<i>Mas madaling nasusukat nang tiyak, maging ang kemikalna may maliit na dami.</i>)	2.03	Disagree	3.56	Strongly Agree
6. It is easier to manipulate laboratory instruments. (<i>Mas madaling nagagamit nang wasto ang mga kagamitan sa laboratoryo.</i>)	2.05	Disagree	3.59	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.01	Disagree	3.59	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.50)", "Disagree (1.51-2.50)", "Agree (2.51-3.50)", "Strongly Agree (3.51-4.50)"

Table 4.2.3 above shows that out of the 6 statements, virtual laboratories obtain 6 disagree while traditional laboratories obtain 6 strongly agree. The entire statement presented is in favor of the traditional laboratory as it reflected an overall weighted mean of 3.59, which is interpreted as "Strongly Agree" compared to the virtual laboratory, which gained an overall weighted mean of 2.01, which signifies "Disagree". The traditional laboratory obtains the highest weighted mean of 3.63, indicating "Strongly Agree" when it comes to easiness in performing

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skills that require eye and hand coordination like trituration and titration, while its lowest weighted mean is 3.52, indicating "Strongly Agree" when it comes to confidence in performing tasks like trituration and titration. On the contrary, virtual laboratory obtained 2.05 as its highest weighted mean, interpreted as "Disagree" when it comes to easiness in manipulating laboratory instruments, while its lowest weighted mean is 1.98, which indicates "Disagree" when it comes to demonstrating skill during experiments. As the result above implies, generally, respondents believe that in the traditional laboratory set-up, eye-hand coordination is more practiced as compared to the virtual laboratory.

Table 4.2.4 Effectiveness in terms of Providing Proper Techniques in Handling Tools and Equipment

Statements	Virtual Laboratory		Traditional Laboratory	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. It is easier to learn proper laboratory techniques. (<i>Mas madaling natutunan ang mga tamang pamamaraan na pang laboratoryo.</i>)	2.03	Disagree	3.66	Strongly Agree
2. It is easier to retain proper techniques in handling tools and equipment. (<i>Mas madaling maisaulo ang tamang pamamaraan/teknik sa paghahavak ng kasangkapan/kagamitan.</i>)	2.02	Disagree	3.65	Strongly Agree
3. Handling of tools and equipment is done with proper etiquette. (<i>Mas nasusunod ang wastong etiquette sa paggamit ng mga kasangkapan at kagamitan.</i>)	2.09	Disagree	3.62	Strongly Agree
4. Accurate taring of apparatuses can be done. (<i>Nagagawang tiyak ang pag-tare ng mga apparatus.</i>)	—	—	3.61	Strongly Agree
5. It is easier to practice proper sanitation of workspace and equipment. (<i>Mas madaling sanayin ang tamang paglilinis ng workspace at kagamitan.</i>)	2.13	Disagree	3.62	Strongly Agree
6. Proper handling of miscellaneous laboratory devices like the microscope can be practiced. (<i>Nagagawang magsanay nang wasto gamit ang miscellaneous na kagamitan sa laboratory tulad ng microscope.</i>)	1.96	Disagree	3.64	Strongly Agree
7. The skills acquired can be used to handle equipment in the actual pharmacy field. (<i>Ang mga kasanayang natutunan ay magagamit sa aktwal na larangan ng pharmasya.</i>)	2.05	Disagree	3.68	Strongly Agree
8. It is easier to yield accurate results by using equipment in experiments. (<i>Mas madaling makakuha ng eksaktong resulta gamit ang mga kagamitan sa pag eeksperimento.</i>)	2.16	Disagree	3.54	Strongly Agree
9. Mistakes are seldom made during experiments. (<i>Mas madalang na nagagawa ang pagkakamali sa mga eksperimento.</i>)	2.30	Disagree	3.24	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.09	Disagree	3.58	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.50)", "Disagree (1.51-2.50)", "Agree (2.51-3.50)", "Strongly Agree (3.51-4.50)"

Table 4.2.4 above shows that out of the 8 statements in the virtual laboratory, it obtained 8 disagree, while out of the 9 statements in the traditional laboratory, it gained 8 strongly agree and 1 agree. The majority of the statements are in favor of the traditional laboratory, as reflected in its overall weighted mean of 3.58, which is interpreted as "Strongly Agree" as compared to the virtual laboratory, which gained an overall weighted mean of 2.09, denoting "Disagree". The highest weighted mean that the traditional laboratory gain is 3.68, which indicates "Strongly Agree" when it comes to acquiring skills that can be used in the actual pharmacy field, while its lowest weighted mean is 3.24, which implies "Agree" when it comes to making few mistakes during experiments. On the other hand, the virtual laboratory got 2.30 as its highest weighted mean, indicating "Disagree" when it comes to making few mistakes during experiments, while its

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lowest weighted mean is 1.96, which implies "Disagree" when it comes to proper handling of miscellaneous laboratory devices. As the result above implies, generally, respondents believe that the traditional laboratory setting is more effective in providing the proper techniques in handling tools and equipment as compared to the virtual laboratory.

4.3 Convenience of Virtual Laboratory Compared to Traditional Laboratory

Table 4.3.1 Convenience in terms of Facilities

Statements	Virtual Laboratory		Traditional Laboratory	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. It is more comfortable to experiment in. (<i>Mas kumportableng mag-eksperimento.</i>)	2.13	Disagree	3.62	Strongly Agree
2. Feels more secure. (<i>Mas ligtas sa pakiramdam magsagawa ng eksperimento.</i>)	2.45	Disagree	3.53	Strongly Agree
3. Experiments can be performed with fewer distractions. (<i>Maaaring isagawa ang mga eksperimento nang may mas kaunting mga distraksyon.</i>)	2.17	Disagree	3.42	Agree
4. Chemicals or reagents readily available. (<i>Ang mga kemikal o reagents ay nakahandang magamit.</i>)	2.29	Disagree	3.60	Strongly Agree
5. Performing experiments is easier because necessities are readily available (e.g. Wifi, computer, cellphone, etc.). (<i>Ang pagsasagawa ng mga eksperimento ay mas madali dahil ang mga pangangailangan ay nakahanda (hal. wifi, computer, cellphone, atbp.)</i>)	2.53	Agree	3.26	Agree
6. Proper and safe waste disposal of materials after an experiment is evident. (<i>Maaari kong ligtas na itapon ang mga basura pagkatapos ng isang eksperimento.</i>)	2.22	Disagree	3.56	Strongly Agree
7. There is less frequency of accidents/injuries. (<i>Nakakaranas ako ng mas kaunting dalas na mga aksidente/pinsala.</i>)	2.73	Agree	2.98	Agree
8. Learning is better due to the aesthetically pleasing environment. (<i>Mas maayos ang pag-aaral dahil sa estetikong kapaligiran.</i>)	2.20	Disagree	3.53	Strongly Agree
9. Students perform experiments without worrying about hurting anybody. (<i>Nakagagawa ang mga estudyante ng mga eksperimento nang hindi nababahala na masaktan ang sinuman.</i>)	2.76	Agree	3.12	Agree
10. Provides proper ventilation for the chemicals being used during experiments. (<i>Nagbibigay ng wastong bentilasyon para sa mga kemikal na ginagamit sa panahon ng mga eksperimento.</i>)	2.18	Disagree	3.59	Strongly Agree
11. Provides a well-structured facility for me to perform experiments well. (<i>Nagbibigay ng isang maayos na pasilidad para sa akin upang maisagawa ko nang maayos ang mga eksperimento.</i>)	2.23	Disagree	3.59	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.35	Disagree	3.44	Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.50)", "Disagree (1.51-2.50)", "Agree (2.51-3.50)", "Strongly Agree (3.51-4.50)"

Table 4.3.1 above shows that out of the 11 statements, the virtual laboratory obtained 8 disagrees and 3 agrees, while the traditional laboratory obtained 7 strongly agree and the remaining 4 as agree. The majority of the statements are in favor of the traditional laboratory, as reflected in its overall weighted mean of 3.44, which is interpreted as "Agree" as compared to the virtual laboratory which gained an overall weighted mean of 2.35 which is interpreted as "Disagree". The highest weighted mean obtained by the traditional laboratory is 3.62, which indicates "Strongly Agree" when it comes to it being more comfortable to experiment in, while its lowest weighted mean is 2.98, which implies "Agree" when it comes to having less frequent accidents or injuries. On the other hand, the virtual laboratory got 2.76 as its highest weighted

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mean which indicates “Agree” when it comes to students performing experiments without worrying about hurting anybody, while its lowest weighted mean is 2.13, which indicated “Disagree” as it is less comfortable to experiment in. As the result above implies, generally, respondents believe that the traditional laboratory setting is more convenient in terms of facilities as compared to the virtual laboratory as it has all the basic necessities in conducting laboratory experiments.

Table 4.3.2 Convenience in terms of Accessibility of Devices, Materials, and Instruments Used

Statements	Virtual Laboratory		Traditional Laboratory	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. It is easier to obtain complete PPE (lab gown, disposable masks, hairnet, and safety eyeglasses). (<i>Mas madaling makakuha ng kumpletong PPE (lab gown, disposable masks, hairnet, at safety eyeglasses).</i>)	2.32	Disagree	3.46	Agree
2. It is easier to perform experiments because instruments are readily available. (<i>Mas madaling magsagawa ng mga eksperimento dahil ang mga instrumento at kagamitan ay madaling makuha.</i>)	2.30	Disagree	3.61	Strongly Agree
3. It is easier to acquire necessary learning materials (e.g. laboratory manual and handouts). (<i>Mas madaling kumuha ng mga kinakailangang materyales sa pag-aaral (hal. laboratory manual at handout).</i>)	2.55	Agree	3.51	Strongly Agree
4. There are readily available materials, therefore, students do not need to purchase any materials. (<i>Mayroon nakahandang magagamit na mga materyales, samakatuwid, hindi na kailangang bumili ng anumang mga materyales.</i>)	2.45	Disagree	3.10	Agree
5. Provides a faster way to finish experiments due to instruments being available. (<i>Nagbibigay ng mas mabilis na paraan upang tapusin ang mga eksperimento dahil sa mga instrument na magagamit.</i>)	2.42	Disagree	3.50	Agree
6. Provides high-end apparatus available for students to get accurate results. (<i>Nagbibigay ng magandang klaseng kagamitan na magagamit ng mga mag-aaral upang makakuha ng mga eksaktong resulta.</i>)	2.24	Disagree	3.51	Strongly Agree
7. Makes it possible to attain the preferred experiment results due to the availability of devices. (<i>Ginagawang posible na makuha ang hinihinging resulta nang eksperimento dahil sa pagkakaroon ng mga kagamitan.</i>)	2.31	Disagree	3.49	Agree
8. Printing out the required modules is trouble-free. (<i>Mas madaling makapag-print ng mga kinakailangang modyul.</i>)	2.69	Agree	3.08	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.41	Disagree	3.41	Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.50)", "Disagree (1.51-2.50)", "Agree (2.51-3.50)", "Strongly Agree (3.51-4.50)"

Table 4.3.2 above shows that out of the 8 statements, the virtual laboratory obtained 6 disagrees and 2 agree, while the traditional laboratory obtained 3 strongly agree and 5 agree. The majority of the statements are in favor of the traditional laboratory, as reflected in its overall weighted mean of 3.41, which is interpreted as “Agree” as compared to the virtual laboratory which gained an overall weighted mean of 2.41, which is interpreted as “Disagree”. The highest weighted mean obtained by the traditional laboratory is 3.61, which indicates “Strongly Agree” when it comes to being able to perform experiments because instruments are readily available in the said laboratory set-up, while its lowest weighted mean is 3.08, which implies “Agree” when it comes to printing out the required modules being trouble-free. On the other hand, the virtual laboratory got 2.69 as its highest weighted mean which indicated “Agree” when it comes to printing out the required modules being trouble-free as well, while its lowest weighted mean is

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2.24, which indicates “Disagree” as it does not provide high-end apparatus available for students to get accurate results. As the result above implies, generally, respondents believe that the traditional laboratory setting is more convenient in terms of accessibility of devices, materials, and instruments used as compared to the virtual laboratory.

Table 4.3.3 Convenience in terms of Getting Assistance from Professors

Statements	Virtual Laboratory		Traditional Laboratory	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. The professor is always available at the time of the class. (<i>Ang mga propesor ay laging naroon sa oras ng klase.</i>)	2.40	Disagree	3.41	Agree
2. It is easier to ask the professors for assistance if the group encountered a problem when experimenting in which laboratory setting. (<i>Mas madaling humingi ng tulong sa mga propesor kung ang grupo ay nakatagpo ng isang problema habang nag-eeksperimento.</i>)	2.31	Disagree	3.60	Strongly Agree
3. Students are not scared to perform a technical activity (e.g. trituration, levigation, etc.) because they know that the professor is ready to assist them. (<i>Hindi natatakot ang mga estudyante na magsagawa ng teknikal na aktibidad (hal. trituration, levigation, atbp.) dahil alam nila na ang propesor ay handing tumulong sa kanila.</i>)	2.39	Disagree	3.36	Agree
4. Students are more confident because they know that the professor is knowledgeable about the protocols once there is an emergency. (<i>Panatag ang loob ng mga estudyante dahil alam nilang may sapat na kaalaman ang mga propesor sa pagresponde kung sa kaling magkaroon ng hindi inaasahang mga pangyayari.</i>)	2.35	Disagree	3.54	Strongly Agree
5. Understanding lessons may depend on the professor's guidance. (<i>Mas naintindihan ang mga aralin nang may kalinawan dahil sa patnubay ng mga propesor.</i>)	2.63	Agree	3.53	Strongly Agree
6. It is faster to get a professor's reply about an inquiry. (<i>Mas mabilis na makakuha ng tugon ng isang propesor tungkol sa isang pagtatanong.</i>)	2.26	Disagree	3.54	Strongly Agree
7. It is easier to approach professors regarding personal matters that refrain a student from being present during the laboratory. (<i>Mas madaling lumapit sa mga propesor tungkol sa mga personal na bagay na pumipigil sa isang estudyante na dumalo sa klase sa laboratoryo.</i>)	2.29	Disagree	3.46	Agree
8. It is easier to approach a professor regarding your progress in the experiment. (<i>Mas madaling lapitan ang propesor ukol sa iyong progreso sa ginagawang eksperimento.</i>)	2.21	Disagree	3.57	Strongly Agree
9. Allows students to not have to suffer silently when confused about a laboratory exercise. (<i>Pinahihintulutan ako na hindi magdusa nang tahimik kapag nalilito tungkol sa isang eksperimentong panglaboratoryo.</i>)	2.21	Disagree	3.47	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.34	Disagree	3.50	Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.50)", "Disagree (1.51-2.50)", "Agree (2.51-3.50)", "Strongly Agree (3.51-4.50)"

Table 4.3.3 above shows that the virtual laboratory gained 8 disagree and 1 agree while the traditional laboratory gained 5 strongly agree and 4 agree. The majority of the statements are in favor of the traditional laboratory as reflected in its overall weighted mean of 3.50 which interprets “Agree” compared to the virtual laboratory with an overall weighted mean of 2.34 which means “Disagree”. The highest weighted mean under the virtual laboratory is 2.63 which indicates “Agree” to understanding lessons may depend on a professor’s guidance while its lowest mean is 2.21 which indicates “Disagree” in 2 statements, when it comes to approaching the professors easier, and allow the students to prevent experiencing silent sufferings every time they are confused about their laboratory exercise. On the other hand, the traditional laboratory gained 3.60 as its highest mean which interprets “Strongly Agree” when it comes to easiness in asking the professors for assistance during the experiment, while its lowest weighted mean is 3.36

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which translates to “Agree” when it comes to students being unafraid of performing a technical activity because they know that the professor is ready to assist them. As the results imply, generally, the respondents believe that the traditional laboratory allows them to get a professor’s assistance more conveniently as compared to the virtual laboratory.

Table 4.3.4 Convenience in terms of Creating an Output

Statements	Virtual Laboratory		Traditional Laboratory	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. It is easier to come up with a way on how to execute the plan in making an output. <i>(Mas madaling makabuo ng paraan kung paano isasagawa ang plano sa paggawa ng output.)</i>	2.40	Disagree	3.49	Agree
2. It is easier to troubleshoot any inaccuracies when implementing the plan for making an output. <i>(Mas madaling solusyunan ang mga pagkakamali sa garwain.)</i>	2.45	Disagree	3.42	Agree
3. It is easier to obtain results in experiments due to the instruments being readily available. <i>(Mas napapadali ang pagkuha ng mga resulta sa mga eksperimento.)</i>	2.39	Disagree	3.53	Strongly Agree
4. Creating an output faster. <i>(Mas mabilis na nakakagawa ng output.)</i>	2.45	Disagree	3.39	Agree
5. Students can get immediate feedback about their output. <i>(Nakakakuha ang mga estudyante ng agarang tugon tungkol sa kanilang output.)</i>	2.35	Disagree	3.50	Agree
6. Students can create accurate output easily because they are able to make early adjustments based on the criteria given. <i>(Ang mga mag-aaral ay kayang makagawa ng output na nakabase sa pamantayan kaya naman nagagawa nila ng mas wasto ang kanilang mga output.)</i>	2.38	Disagree	3.46	Agree
7. The possibility of acquiring better grades with output may be due to the higher accuracy of the process done. <i>(Mas mataas ang posibilidad na makakuha nang mahusay na marka sa output na sanhi ng tamang proseso.)</i>	2.43	Disagree	3.43	Agree
8. It is much easier to understand the process of making an output due to the comprehensive discussion of the professors. <i>(Mas madaling maunawaan ang proseso ng paggawa ng output dahil sa komprehensibong talakayan ng mga propesor.)</i>	2.30	Disagree	3.53	Strongly Agree
9. It is easier to manage information in a group to create better output. <i>(Mas madaling pamahalaan ang mga impormasyon nang pangkatan para makalikha ng mas maayos na output.)</i>	2.31	Disagree	3.55	Strongly Agree
10. Outputs are made with confidence due to less confusion regarding the procedure taught by the professor. <i>(Mas may kumpiyansa sa mga output na ginawa dahil mas komprehensibo ang ginawang talakayan ng propesor.)</i>	2.30	Disagree	3.54	Strongly Agree
11. It is easy to obtain experimental results. <i>(Madaling makakuha ng mga resulta.)</i>	2.39	Disagree	3.59	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.38	Disagree	3.49	Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.50)", "Disagree (1.51-2.50)", "Agree (2.51-3.50)", "Strongly Agree (3.51-4.50)"

Table 4.3.4 above shows that the virtual laboratories acquired disagree with all the statements presented while the traditional laboratory gained 5 strongly agree and 6 agree. The majority of the statements are in favor of the traditional laboratory as reflected in its overall weighted mean of 3.49 which interprets “Agree” compared to the virtual laboratory with an overall weighted mean of 2.38 which means “Disagree”. The highest weighted mean under virtual laboratory is 2.45 indicating “Disagree” in 2 statements, when it comes to the easiness of troubleshooting inaccuracies when implementing plan to make an output, and creating an output faster. Its lowest mean is 2.30 which indicates “Disagree” in 2 statements, with understanding the process of making an output due to the comprehensive discussion of the professors is easier, and outputs are made with confidence due to less confusion regarding the procedures taught by the professor. On the other hand, the traditional laboratory gained 3.59 as its highest mean which interprets “Strongly Agree” when it pertains to obtaining experimental results being easy, while its lowest weighted mean is 3.39 which translates to “Agree” when it comes to students creating

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an output faster. As the results imply, generally, the respondents believe that the traditional laboratory allows them to create output more conveniently as compared to the virtual laboratory.

Table 4.3.5 Convenience in terms of Being in a Group

Statements	Virtual Laboratory		Traditional Laboratory	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. It is easier to plan for the experiment as a group. <i>(Mas madaling magplano para sa eksperimento bilang isang grupo.)</i>	2.29	Disagree	3.54	Strongly Agree
2. Brainstorming is easier. <i>(Mas madali ang palitan ng ideya.)</i>	2.25	Disagree	3.59	Strongly Agree
3. It is easier to provide ideas and receive feedback from groupmates about individual performance. <i>(Mas napapadali ang pagbibigay ng mga ideya at tugon mula sa mga kagrupong tungkol sa indibidwal na gawain.)</i>	2.28	Disagree	3.59	Strongly Agree
4. It is easier to understand the task given with the help of my groupmates. <i>(Mas nakakatulong na mas madaling maintindihan ang gawain dahil sa tulong ng mga kagrupong.)</i>	2.28	Disagree	3.63	Strongly Agree
5. It is easier to simplify tasks as a group. <i>(Mas madali ang mga gawain bilang isang grupo.)</i>	2.38	Disagree	3.59	Strongly Agree
6. Develop strong communication skills due to participating in a group. <i>(Magkaroon ng malakas na kasanayan sa komunikasyon dahil sa pakikilahok sa isang grupo.)</i>	–	–	3.55	Strongly Agree
7. Tasks are performed faster in a group. <i>(Mas mabilis na natatapos ang mga gawain kapag nasa isang grupo.)</i>	2.40	Disagree	3.57	Strongly Agree
8. Groupmates do not delay results for the experiment. <i>(Hindi naaantala ng mga kagrupong ang resulta ng eksperimento.)</i>	2.21	Disagree	3.36	Agree
9. Working with a group is not hassle. <i>(Hindi abala ang pagsasagawa ng gawain bilang isang grupo.)</i>	2.31	Disagree	3.41	Agree
10. Everyone takes part in bringing the outcome <i>(Ang bawat isa ay nakikibahagi sa paggawa ng resulta)</i>	2.46	Disagree	3.52	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.32	Disagree	3.54	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.50)", "Disagree (1.51-2.50)", "Agree (2.51-3.50)", "Strongly Agree (3.51-4.50)"

Table 4.3.5 above shows that the virtual laboratory gained 9 disagree while the traditional laboratories gained 8 strongly agree and 2 agree. The majority of the statements are in favor of the traditional laboratory as reflected in its overall weighted mean of 3.54 which interprets as “Strongly Agree” as compared to the virtual laboratory which acquired an overall mean of 2.32 which signifies “Disagree”. The virtual laboratory gained 2.46 as its highest weighted mean, which interprets as "Disagree" when it comes to everyone taking part in bringing the outcome of the activity, while its lowest weighted mean got 2.21 indicating "Disagree" when it comes to groupmates do not delay the results of the experiment. Meanwhile, the traditional laboratory got its highest weighted mean of 3.63, indicating "Strongly Agree" when it comes to finding it easier to understand the task given with the help of the groupmates, while its lowest mean is 3.36 which indicates "Agree" when it comes groupmates do not delay the results of the experiment. As the results indicate, respondents, in general, believe that the traditional laboratory set-up is more convenient when it comes to doing tasks or experiments in a group as compared to the virtual laboratory.

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Table 4.3.6 Convenience in terms of Organizing Own Time

Statements	Virtual Laboratory		Traditional Laboratory	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I am much more organized in terms of prioritizing things. (Ako ay mas organisado sa mga tuntunin ng pagbibigay-prayoridad sa mga bagay.)	2.40	Disagree	3.42	Agree
2. I can manage my time well. (Gamay ko ang aking oras.)	2.47	Disagree	3.35	Agree
3. It allows me to have enough time to review even after doing experiments. (Nagbibigay-daan sa akin na magkaroon ng sapat na oras upang masuring muli kahit na matapos na ang paggawa ng mga eksperimento.)	2.44	Disagree	3.24	Agree
4. I experience less stress because of easier time management. (Nakakaranas ako ng mas kaunting stress dahil sa mas madaling pamamahala ng oras.)	2.28	Disagree	3.18	Agree
5. It allows me to have a better work-life balance. (Nagbibigay-daan sa akin na magkaroon ng mas magandang balance sa gawain-buhay.)	2.37	Disagree	3.34	Agree
6. I procrastinate less. (Nagagawa kong hindi magpaliban ng mga gawain.)	2.30	Disagree	3.33	Agree
7. I am less overwhelmed with the tasks given. (Hindi ako gaanong nababahala sa mga gawaing ibinigay.)	2.23	Disagree	3.22	Agree
8. I can manage my sleep schedule better. (Mas na papamahalaan ko ang aking iskedyul ng pagtulog.)	2.49	Disagree	3.11	Agree
9. I can study well. (Mas nakakapag-aral ako ng mabuti.)	2.25	Disagree	3.42	Agree
10. I finish all or most requirements needed on time. (Nagagawa kong tapusin ang lahat o karamihan ng mga kinakailangan sa takdang-oras.)	2.52	Agree	3.41	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	2.38	Disagree	3.30	Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.50)", "Disagree (1.51-2.50)", "Agree (2.51-3.50)", "Strongly Agree (3.51-4.50)"

Table 4.3.6 above shows that the virtual laboratory gained 9 disagree and 1 agree while the traditional laboratory gained agree in all of the statements. The majority of the statements are in favor of the traditional laboratory as reflected in its overall weighted mean of 3.30 which is interpreted as "Agree" as compared to the virtual laboratory which acquired an overall mean of 2.38 which signifies "Disagree". The virtual laboratory got 2.52 as the highest weighted mean, which indicates "Agree" when it comes to students being able to finish all or most of the requirements on time, while its lowest weighted mean is 2.23 which means "Disagree" when it comes to being less overwhelmed with the tasks given. On the other hand, the traditional laboratory gained its highest weighted mean of 3.42 which indicates "Agree" in two statements, particularly when it comes to being more organized in terms of prioritizing things as well as being able to study well, while its lowest mean is 3.11 which means "Agree" when it comes to managing their sleep schedule better. As the result indicates, the general respondents believe that traditional laboratories are more convenient when it comes to organizing their own time as compared to virtual laboratories.

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Table 4.4 Paired T-test: Significant Difference between Traditional and Virtual Laboratories in terms of Effectiveness, Convenience, and Overall Perception and Attitude of Students

	Laboratories	Mean	SD	t	df	p	Decision	Remarks
Effectiveness	Traditional	3.277	0.361	17.272	172	<0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Virtual	2.364	0.617					
Convenience	Traditional	3.447	0.448	15.984	172	<0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Virtual	2.361	0.719					
Perception and attitude	Traditional	3.362	0.387	17.202	172	<0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Virtual	2.363	0.643					

Note: "If p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject ho, otherwise, failed to reject ho"

Table 4.4 above shows the results obtained by performing a paired t-test analysis to measure the difference between traditional and virtual laboratory set-ups in terms of convenience, effectiveness, as well as perception and attitude of pharmacy students. It is shown that all three "Effectiveness" (<0.001), "Convenience" (<0.001), and "Perception and attitude" (<0.001), have a p-value of less than 0.05, which implies significant results. Therefore, traditional laboratories are significantly different compared to virtual laboratories in terms of their effectiveness, convenience, and overall perception and attitude of students. This implies that the majority of the respondents preferred the traditional laboratory as compared to the virtual laboratory as reflected in the mean of both set-ups wherein in all conditions, the traditional laboratory gained a higher mean.

5.0 Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendation

This chapter consists of a summary of the results and findings, conclusions, as well as recommendations. This chapter elaborates and explains the importance of the findings, explains every point presented to address the problems stated by the researchers, as well as suggests possible points to improve by future researchers.

5.1 Summary of Findings

A good laboratory setting is needed for students to have a great learning outcome. The research was done to compare, contrast, and know which laboratory setting among traditional and virtual laboratories gives a better learning outcome to third and fourth-year students. This section summarized the results, presented answers to the problems, and described and interpreted the significance of the findings.

The demographics of the respondents are composed of age, gender, and year level. In general, it shows that the majority of the respondents are aged 21 years old, female, and third-year pharmacy students.

In terms of the difference between the effectiveness of traditional and virtual laboratories, it has been identified that there is a significant difference between the results of traditional and virtual laboratories. In terms of the cost-friendliness of laboratory settings, the statements' overall weighted mean suggests that the respondents "Agree" with most of the statements under the virtual laboratory. On the contrary, respondents "Disagree" with most of the statements under the traditional laboratory. The results thus indicate that the respondents find the virtual laboratory a more cost-friendly setting than the traditional laboratory, implying that respondents find the traditional laboratory as a setting where they need to put forth more money as compared to the virtual laboratory, simply because the virtual laboratory does not implement experimentation that requires chemicals and other laboratory materials. For the learning delivery, respondents "Strongly Agree" with most of the statements under the traditional laboratory while they "Disagree" with most of the statements under the virtual laboratory, indicating that the learning delivery in a traditional laboratory is much better than in the virtual laboratory. This implies that respondents find the traditional laboratory as a setting where the lessons are easily understood and better explained than the virtual laboratory. The participants also believe that a traditional laboratory provides better learning modes and that the existence of the library inevitably improves their study habits. Proper disposal of materials is also easily learned. For manual

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dexterity, respondents "Strongly Agree" with most of the statements under the traditional laboratory while they "Disagree" with most of the statements under the virtual laboratory, which indicates that the traditional laboratory helps improve the manual dexterity of students as compared to the virtual laboratory. It implies that respondents find the traditional laboratory as a setting where performing tasks that need eye-hand coordination is easier than the virtual laboratory, where the development of eye-hand coordination is somewhat limited. In terms of providing proper techniques for handling instruments and equipment, the statements' overall weighted mean suggests that the respondents "Strongly Agree" with most of the statements under the traditional laboratory. On the contrary, respondents "Disagree" with most of the statements about the virtual laboratory, which means that learning the proper techniques for handling instruments and equipment in a traditional laboratory is much better than in a virtual laboratory. This implies that respondents find the traditional laboratory as a setting where they can easily learn and apply the proper way of handling tools and equipment compared to a virtual laboratory where they need to exert effort to analyze the proper technique in handling laboratory instruments. In addition to this, participants also practice accurate taring of apparatus, proper sanitation, and proper etiquette during the traditional laboratory. The pharmacy students also have confidence that the skills they learn during the traditional laboratory can be used in the actual field of pharmacy.

In terms of the difference between the convenience of traditional and virtual laboratories, it has been identified that there is a significant difference in the results of traditional and virtual laboratories. In terms of the facilities of the laboratory setting, respondents "Agree" with most of the statements under the traditional laboratory while "Disagree" with most of the statements under the virtual laboratory, indicating that the traditional laboratory provides better facilities than the virtual laboratory. This indicates that the respondents find the traditional laboratory as a setting where they feel more secure in performing experiments and are more at ease working since the laboratory instruments there are complete compared to the virtual laboratory where performing experiments feels uncertain. This also proves that the respondents prefer and like the environment and aesthetics of the traditional laboratory for it is comfortable, and has proper ventilation. For accessibility of the laboratory setting, respondents "Agree" with most of the statements under the traditional laboratory. On the contrary, respondents "Disagree" with most of the statements under the virtual laboratory, implying that the traditional laboratory is more accessible than the virtual laboratory. This implies that respondents find the traditional laboratory as a setting where it is easy to acquire laboratory materials compared to the virtual laboratory,

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where obtaining laboratory materials is somehow complicated. Additionally, students can also have access to high-end laboratory apparatus during traditional laboratory activities. As to getting assistance from professors, the statements' overall weighted mean suggests that the respondents "Agree" on statements under the traditional laboratory. On the contrary, respondents "Disagree" with the statements under the virtual laboratory, denoting that it is better to get assistance from professors in the traditional laboratory compared to the virtual laboratory. The results imply that respondents find the traditional laboratory as a setting where approaching the professors is trouble-free because they can see the professors right away as compared to the virtual laboratory where professors also experience barriers in conducting online classes making them unable to assist sometimes. In terms of creating output, respondents "Agree" with the statements under the traditional laboratory. On the contrary, respondents "Disagree" with the statements under the virtual laboratory, indicating that the traditional laboratory creates an output better than the virtual laboratory. The results imply that respondents find the traditional laboratory a setting where creating output is easier and faster than the virtual laboratory, where tasks take time. Participants have easier time troubleshooting inaccuracies in their experimental outputs leading to easier obtaining of results and they can also get immediate feedback which leads to the possibility of acquiring better grades during the traditional laboratory. In terms of being in a group, the statements' overall weighted mean suggests that the respondents "Strongly Agree" on statements under the traditional laboratory. On the contrary, respondents "Disagree" with the statements under the virtual laboratory, indicating that it is better to be in a group in the traditional laboratory than in the virtual laboratory. It implies that respondents find the traditional laboratory a setting where it is less hassle to communicate and work with the group than the virtual laboratory, where working with the group is somehow a hassle. Because in the traditional laboratory, scheduling a meeting is easy unlike in a virtual laboratory where most of the students experience barriers in participating in online meetings like having a poor internet connection, household tasks, and the like. Meanwhile, respondents "Agree" with most of the statements in the traditional laboratory about organizing their own time while "Disagree" with most of the statements in the virtual laboratory, indicating that the student is better at organizing their time in the traditional laboratory than in the virtual laboratory. The results imply that respondents find traditional laboratories as a laboratory setting where they manage their time well than in a virtual laboratory where balancing time requires a lot of discipline. Students also experience less stress, have better work-life balance, and are less overwhelmed with tasks during the traditional laboratory.

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Although almost all statements are in favor of the traditional laboratory, a few relevant exemptions were recorded in the responses that highlight the good part of the virtual laboratory. It is predominantly observed under the cost-effectiveness survey questions. The students believe that in the virtual laboratory, less money is used in paying for PPE, materials, printed handouts, transportation, snacks, fees for lab equipment breakage, chemicals, laboratory modules, and locker rents. Participants also stated that they agree that performing experiments is easier because they have necessities such as wifi, phones, and the like. Additionally, being in the virtual laboratory also means that there is a lesser frequency of someone getting hurt due to laboratory accidents. The acquisition and printing of materials such as handouts are also easier for students in the virtual laboratory. The respondents also agree that understanding the lessons depends on the professor's guidance during the virtual laboratory. Lastly, most of the participants stated that they can finish all or almost all of their tasks on time during the virtual laboratory.

In terms of the difference in students' perception and attitude between traditional and virtual laboratories, it has been identified that there is a significant difference in the perception between traditional and virtual laboratories. The results indicate that the scores obtained for the traditional class were significantly higher compared to the scores obtained for its virtual counterpart. Thus, considering the responses for both convenience and effectiveness of the laboratories, it can be implied that the traditional laboratory is more preferred by the students than the virtual laboratory.

5.2 Conclusion

This section answers the statement of the problem as well as confirms if the hypothesis is accepted or not.

For the first statement of the problem that needs to be addressed, the result shows a significant difference between the effectiveness of traditional and virtual laboratories implying the rejection of the null hypothesis and retention of the alternative hypothesis. The same with the second statement of the problem as the results imply a significant difference between the convenience of traditional and virtual laboratories insinuating the rejection of the null hypothesis. For the last statement of the problem, the results show that there is a significant difference in students' perceptions and attitudes between traditional and virtual laboratories.

The two laboratories differ when it comes to being cost-friendly, learning delivery, providing manual dexterity, providing proper technique in handling tools and equipment,

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facilities, accessibility of devices, materials, and instruments used, getting assistance from professors, creating an output, being in a group, as well as how students organize their time. And all of these conditions, except for being cost-friendly, are in favor of traditional laboratories. This means pharmacy students tend to think that even though the expenses are much lower in the virtual laboratories, it does not mean that the quality of education and the experience are still the same. It suggests that both third and fourth-year pharmacy students generally preferred the learning delivery, development of skills, facilities, accessibility, as well as management of works in traditional laboratory settings which calls for the attention of not just the University but the education system as well, that courses which require skills, focus, and concentration should be implemented in a face-to-face setting as the system itself is not prepared for implementing virtual classes.

5.3 Recommendations

The researchers are aware of the limitations of this research; thereby, this section is dedicated to future researchers who wish to explore this topic further. The population and sample size are limited only to the private institution located in Valenzuela City, particularly students that are currently enrolled in B.S. Pharmacy. Therefore, a larger sample size drawn from the country's population would be strongly suggested to assess students' perceptions and attitudes towards traditional and virtual laboratories.

The following are sought to be recommended based on the results of the study:

5.3.1 Future researchers may include comparisons of student perception and attitude based on gender to determine if this is a significant factor.

5.3.2 Future researchers may include other courses that implement both virtual and traditional laboratories.

5.3.3 Future researchers may include other universities that offer both traditional and virtual laboratories.

5.3.4 Future researchers may use a mixed approach (qualitative and quantitative) to consider the personal insights of the participants.

6.0 Glossary of terms

COVID 19. According to World Health Organization, the Coronavirus Disease 2019 caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus is an infectious disease, in which the majority of people infected with this, may show mild to moderate respiratory symptoms. Due to its high spreadability, this disease traveled across the world causing a pandemic.

Manual dexterity. The ability to carry out regulated motions by hands under particular situations makes the task looks easy when it is not. This can be developed by mastering skills like writing, holding and releasing items, puzzles as well as building toys from an early age (Cambridge Dictionary).

Online class. This refers to a course taken online that develops the soft skills of students and is done either synchronous or asynchronously (Moore & Pearson, 2017). This term can also be used interchangeably with distance learning, flexible learning, or virtual class since this is done using applications and devices which suit the convenience of the students.

Pandemic. A pandemic is a disease epidemic that affects many nations or continents at the same time. It has a larger impact as the mortality is higher compared to an epidemic. When it became evident that the sickness was severe and spreading rapidly across a large region, the World Health Organization (WHO) will categorize it as a pandemic (Robinson, 2020).

Traditional laboratories. It is a place wherein students can get hands-on experience in scientific experiments which leads to the development of knowledge and skills of the students (Mcdaniel, 2010). In this specific study, the term traditional laboratory is used interchangeably with face-to-face laboratory, and these two terms refer to the place wherein actual usage of instruments and experimentation are observed before the COVID-19 pandemic.

Virtual laboratories. It is a laboratory course done virtually using an app like Zoom which requires a camera, microphone, and other devices (Darr et. al., 2021). In this specific study, aside from conducting virtual conferences, the virtual laboratory also consists of home-based experiments, Labster simulation as well as worksheets.

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APPENDIX A

Review of Related Literature and Studies

A.1 Related Literature

A. 1.1. Local Literature

The pandemic brings a lot of unexpected events in the lives of many. This phenomenon created a lot of difficulties, as it greatly affects the economy, jobs, and even the educational system, which pushes everyone into a huge adjustment to cope and continue to move forward. A lot of Filipinos suffered and each individual played a role in making adjustments to the so-called new normal. The pandemic that emerged in 2019 has made significant effects to education systems, such as school closure and eventually, the shift to online, distance learning in all levels. The new normal in education includes online classes, sometimes called virtual learning, blended learning, distance learning, or flexible learning. The online class consists of two parts, namely, synchronous and asynchronous. In a study conducted by Taracatac (2021), she observed that there is a significant difference between the performance of the students in synchronous and asynchronous learning. She compared the scores of the pre-test and post-test of the students and it turns out that the student's performance after the synchronous discussion is better than before the discussion. Thereby, this may imply that teaching lives via the Zoom and Google meet applications is essential in the effectiveness of the learning of the students. Furthermore, it also implies that if the students are more self-studying, there is a higher probability that the actual major points in a topic will be missed or misunderstood. The study conducted by Rotas and Cahapay (2020), on the other hand, which aimed to know the struggles in online learning of university students in the Philippines amidst the COVID-19 crisis, showed that the students who enrolled in a tertiary institution struggled in different categories, namely, unstable internet connection, insufficient learning resources, electric power interruptions, ambiguous learning matters, overloaded lesson activities, limited teacher scaffolds, poor peer communication, conflict with home responsibilities, poor learning environment, financial difficulty, physical health compromises, and mental health problems. The researchers recommended that despite all the struggles that are present, these difficulties should be used as an eye-opener for all and to consider the inputs for further improvement of the current educational method.

As eloquently stated by Estipular and Roleda (2018), teaching science in terms of experiments and visualizations requires time and effort. And considering today's setting, there is an increase in the difficulty in providing accurate and precise scientific education to students.

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They also reiterated that laboratories are a vital part of the willingness of the students to learn as it allows them to discover new ideas that will scaffold their knowledge. Additionally, schools need to acquire not just the most up-to-date but also high-quality laboratory equipments to ensure that student understands all of the concepts being discussed. To understand a concept, one must seek beyond books and traditional classroom education, as well as actual manipulation of real items and materials (Dela Cruz & Mendoza, 2018). Despite this, the importance of laboratory sessions to student learning must not be compromised, and an alternative approach to certain issues is necessary. And the best option for that is the virtual laboratory used as a learning aid in a variety of fields and industries, including surgery training, phobia treatment or therapy in healthcare, explosives training in the military, firefighting training in the fire department, and space training in aeronautics. Furthermore, the activities done in a virtual laboratory can save money, time, and effort for the students. In addition to this, virtual labs create an interactive and safe environment that permits the emergence of student involvement. Universities in the Philippines are obligated to envision the future of e-learning that also involves virtual laboratories via Canvass and Labster. The practical skills obtained through performed experiments provide students with a more profound sense of the concepts, more than when it is taught to them verbally. As time progresses, so must the learners and to progress, there is a need for adaptation of flexible learning. Virtual laboratories support flexible learning by having high accessibility to the students.

A. 1.2. Foreign Literature

According to Pandya and Lodha (2021), due to the pandemic, schools are pushed to transition from traditional learning methods to distance learning or online class. Virtual laboratories are simulated versions of traditional laboratories that use a learner-centered approach in which students are provided virtual representations of real-world things that are used in traditional laboratories. It can offer students the opportunity to investigate situations that cannot be tested in real time by speeding up or slowing downtime. Virtual laboratories save time as compared to traditional hands-on labs. It is also useful for learning complex topics like relativity and experiments which would not be possible in a regular laboratory setting. Despite all of the benefits, several researchers pointed out certain drawbacks, such as students' lack of hands-on experience (Faour&Ayoubi, 2018; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2020).

All instructors at all levels around the world were challenged to teach classes online during the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak and public lockout. Today, people consider Internet use as a routine activity, and they expect to have access to a diverse range of resources that are given

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to them in auditory, visual, and even tactile formats that are tailored to their specific needs. Since the first systems were developed years ago, the evolution of online laboratories has undergone significant modifications. Online laboratories are computer programs that enable students, professors, and researchers to carry out experiments from a distance. An online laboratory, which students can run remotely over the internet, can give students significant practical experience in addition to the available hands-on laboratories (Auer, Azad, Edwards, & Jong, 2018). As stated by Babincakova and Bernard (2020), chemical education is more difficult to transition to distance learning than non-science courses due to the experimental nature of the topic. Experiments are extremely important in chemistry education because they provide insight into the basis of scientific knowledge and they promote the development of scientific thinking in students. According to the study conducted by Babincakova and Bernard (2020), the sudden transition from face to face learning to online learning, made various schools and teachers to prepare virtual laboratories for the students through video-recorded demonstrations, live demonstrations of experiments, and virtual and remote laboratories. Keeping schools closed to in-person learning in the fall of 2020, on the other hand, poses potential educational dangers. In-person learning experiences help students of all ages in ways that remote learning cannot fully imitate. For young children and children with disabilities, the educational risks of lengthy-distance learning may be greater. Furthermore, if virtual learning is not implemented carefully, it carries the risk of worsening inequities in access to high-quality education among different demographic groups and communities.

Many educators found themselves quickly switching to remote learning without the necessary knowledge, skills, or resources as the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted education around the world in early 2020. This resulted in less than ideal learning experiences for many higher education students. Several public-sector administrators expressed interest in faculty certification for training, with one revealing that teachers at one of the foreign universities will be awarded a certificate upon completion. According to a poll, students from public institutions did not respond favorably, believing that they require a staff that is well-trained and technologically up-to-date for the long term following the upcoming semester. One student at a private university claimed that her professors did not know how to use technology and that some of them even told pupils what to do. They went on to say that the transition to online was a disaster and that many of them were unprepared to make the adjustments.

As eloquently stated by Leshner and Scherer (2021), the students' well-being is linked to their academic and professional success, yet even before the COVID-19 pandemic hits the entire

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world, mental health is a problem for both students and faculty staff, however, it became more evident and the cases arise due to the pandemic itself, and other factors like economic problems and killings. According to their data, about 40 percent of college students experience mental health problems and by saying mental health includes depression, schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, as well as an anxiety disorder. On the other hand, 60 percent of college students are eager to seek help with their mental health problems, however, they find it difficult nowadays since universities are closed and their programs are online. College students are severely affected by the said phenomena compared to other levels as they will soon transition from being a student to professionals. Thus, they must develop their skills, however, since conducting classes is not allowed, it affected the career-decision making of college students. Other than that, the stress from online classes caused the students to manifest physical symptoms like headache, backache, irritation and watery eyes, ear problems, as well as fatigue. On the psychological effect, college students tend to experience a lack of motivation, loneliness, overthinking, anxiety, depression, sleep disruptions and deprivation, anger, as well as poor concentration on a task. Most students were not able to enroll due to financial matters. Online education changes all components of teaching and learning in higher education. According to Kebritchiet. al. (2017), there are continued reports of high dropout rates and achievement problems in this online setup. They believe that inadequate resources, internet accessibility, and flexibility of online courses made an integral part of online education. In line with that, as the pandemic grows, financial instability also added to the issues brought by the current situation, knowing that online learning requires technologies, the internet, and other resources. The three major categories that were identified in the study involve the issues associated with online learners such as their expectations, readiness, identity, and participation in online courses; instructor's issues which involve their time management and teaching strategies; and also the content development regarding the incorporation of multimedia in content, role of instructional strategies, and other considerations.

Universities should increase their effort or change their approach to dealing with students' problems. For instance, the institution should change its approach to a multi-pronged approach that deals with the prevention, determination of high-risk students, efficient community-based approaches, treatment services, as well as relapse prevention, and post-treatment support. Listening to the perspectives of students, considering the financial situation of the students in their mental, as well as extending their services could minimize the effect of the mental health problems during this pandemic (Leshner& Scherer, 2021). Moreover, to improve and enhance the effectiveness of online teaching and learning, higher education needs to offer training for students, professional development for teachers, and technical support for content development.

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As they engage in the process of scientific discovery and prepare to design and conduct their study, students are drawn to these authentic and tangible tools (Carlin, Brown & Benjamin, 2017; Dahlberg & Higginbotham, 2021).

As stated by Schweingruber, Dibner, & Bond (2020), staffing will be a huge concern if and when schools reopen. Because of the health hazards, a considerable part of school workers are in high-risk age groups or are afraid to return to in-person schooling. Furthermore, some of the measures for minimizing COVID-19 transmission within schools, such as keeping smaller class sizes and providing both in-person and virtual learning will necessitate the hiring of additional instructional personnel. Neto, Souza, and Gomes (2016) mentioned that universities are increasingly implementing remote access laboratories. A traditional, hands-on laboratory experience is preferable, but it is not always possible. The standard technologies used to assist educational systems do not fulfill the individual needs of any situation. Different learning models and new learning tools have had a significant impact, resulting in an inevitable education revolution. The invention of new learning techniques and methodologies, where education and technology have come together and combined, has resulted in a new generation of students who learned through digital tools. Lucas et.al. (2019), added that while simulation can provide a safe environment in which students can practice and implement their knowledge and experience without putting anyone at risk, it cannot replace the authenticity of the traditional laboratory. Moreover, this strategy may include online tools like YouTube educational resources, video game-like dispensing simulators that use virtual patients, hands-on laboratories to practice techniques, and/or use specific equipment like point-of-care testing devices, and role-plays to standardize patients' live experiences. Students have enrolled in a virtual world in which they can participate in different simulated activities. Following that, as the demand for virtual simulations increases during this pandemic, the use of Labster simulation becomes more essential. Virtual laboratories are capable of enhancing the technical and scientific education of the students. Both physical and virtual laboratories can achieve similar learning outcomes, such as interaction with theoretical concepts, hypothesis development and testing, and data collection and analysis, as well as developing teamwork, inquiry skills, and increasing interest in science. Studies on the performance of students that take science-related subjects have shown that the utilization of simulations like Labster, improves conceptual learning, retention, motivation, and study intensity of the students. Moreover, students have also shown a positive outlook on virtual and online alternative laboratories. Furthermore, it is shown that students using virtual labs are less likely to be distracted by measurement errors or multiday procedures that can get complicated and often lead to "failure" while instantly producing data for reflection, allowing instructors to identify

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students' understanding (Alvarez, 2021). However, for instance, in microbiological laboratories, different techniques and usage of actual machines are essential for students to get accurate results in their experiments because films and simulations will not be able to completely develop these skills (Noel et. al., 2020).

A.2. Related Studies

A. 2.1. Local Studies

The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in a significant change from traditional to online distant education, posing numerous challenges to our learning delivery methods. In the study “Online Distance Learning: Thematic Study on the Challenges Faced by Educare College Inc. Primary Pupils” by Belgica, et. al (2020), they discovered the problems of primary students at Educare College, Inc. in the Online Distance Learning mode. To synthesize and identify the obstacles during online classes, the researchers used a phenomenological approach and thematic analysis, which included face-to-face and online interviews, watching recorded Zoom sessions, and observations. The result of the study shows the challenges that students face during online classes, such as poor internet connection, poor comprehension, and recall, and lack of concentration, motivation, and interaction. In conclusion, the researchers recommended that the students, along with their parents and instructors, work together to lessen the effect of these challenges.

Similarly, in the study, “Barriers to Online Learning in the Time of COVID-19: A National Survey of Medical Students in the Philippines” by Baticulon, et al. (2021), the researchers tackled the barriers to online learning. The said study was conducted to identify the hurdles of online learning from the perspective of medical students in the country. Demographics, medical school information, access to technological resources, study habits, living conditions, self-assessment of capacity for and perceived barriers to online learning, and proposed interventions were obtained using a combination of multiple-choice, Likert scale, and open-ended questions. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Nonparametric tests were used to compare responses amongst student subgroups. The result of the study shows that only 1,505 students (41%) said they were physically and mentally capable of participating in online learning under the current

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circumstances. Five types of hurdles were identified: technological, individual, home, institutional, and communal barriers.

As indicated in other studies several public schools have been defied by the inadequacy of science laboratory facilities and equipment, including learning materials needed in performing activities. For this reason, other professors may resort to skipping other laboratory experiments when improvising materials is not possible which may delay the comprehension of some proficiency necessary for the learners. To address these challenges, science, technology, and innovation must be prioritized in the country, and effective and efficient science education is its critical component. The laboratory is where the individual or group of students learns through observation, practice, and hands-on experiments including materials and phenomena, that give them chances to relate to and strengthen some theoretical concepts learned in class (Abas & Marasigan, 2020). Laboratory becomes the heart of science in which individuals could put theory into practice. For the past years, the traditional type of education focuses more on instructing knowledge to students through instruction, simply inserted with classroom discourse of scientific discovery. Moreover, laboratory experiments are a good form of experimental learning where models denote concrete experience and have physical contact with objects of study resulting in an effective mode of learning (Larida, et al., 2021).

Santos and Prudente (2021) eloquently stated that when technology becomes more accessible and refined, assimilating technology into the educational environment is foreseeable. Virtual laboratories are the recreation of the traditional hands-on experiments wherein virtual demonstrations are applied. To integrate the effect of virtual settings on science education, the meta-analysis discovered studies that implemented virtual laboratory experiments compared to traditional laboratory set-ups. Moreover, the subject area and level of study were measured as a subgroup to corroborate if virtual laboratory experiments are effective in the identified subgroups. There are a total of 15 studies involved and analyzed in the meta-analysis and most of the studies made use of the virtual laboratory for science disciplines including Biology, Chemistry, Earth Science, and Physics. Upon conducting the meta-analysis, the researchers produced results inconsistent with the preceding efforts to identify the overall effects of virtual

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simulations in educational environments. The study also revealed that those students who received teaching using a desktop virtual setup overtook those who are engaged in traditional setups and demonstrate well performance wherein they focus more on the practical and physical areas rather than the variables being discovered in the experiment. Furthermore, another factor that might have caused increased cognitive results is the student's exposure time, wherein hands-on experiments let the students repeat experiments without added cost which gives them more opportunities to understand the underlying concepts being studied.

A. 2.2. Foreign Studies

According to the review article by Gamage et al., (2020), the spread of the novel coronavirus has affected education at a large number of universities around the world, either partially or completely (COVID-19). As a result, an increasing number of universities have taken the necessary actions to adapt their curriculum, including converting laboratory activities to an online or blended delivery method. With that, students have had limited or no access to laboratory facilities, and face-to-face education has been prohibited. In light of the COVID-19 pandemic, this study examines how universities are delivering teaching and laboratory activities remotely, as well as the possible implications on student learning. For instance, consider the utilization of web-based activities. Medical students frequently use online simulated laboratory activities as a cost-effective alternative to traditional wet laboratories. This was discussed in the study of Brockman et al., (2020) which examines the student's perception of online and in-person laboratory experience. An online survey was used to gather feedback from students about their lab experience. As a result, the analysis showed that, while students are enthusiastic about digital online lab activities, the vast majority of students still want a combination of online and in-person, hands-on lab activities.

In a study "Comparison of Pharmacy Students' Performance in a Laboratory Course Delivered Live versus by Virtual Facilitation" by Darr et. al. (2021), they compared the academic achievement and student impressions of an outpatient pharmacy practice laboratory course taught in a typical laboratory setting to the virtual facilitation. The respondents involved are 160 and 69 of them were taught in a traditional setting while 91 students were taught using a virtual setting a year after. Major evaluations, individual test questions, and final course grades were used to evaluate students' academic performance. At the end of each course offering, each set of students received a course and instructor review. Students who completed the live traditional laboratory

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course in 2016 received a 90.1 % final course mark, whereas students who completed the remotely facilitated laboratory course in 2017 received an 89.6 % final course grade. Students in the remotely facilitated course had a lower mean score on course evaluations. Between 2016 and 2017, there was no substantial variation in scores between individual course and instructor assessments. Between 2016 and 2017, there was no significant variation in students' grades on midterm and final objective structured clinical examinations and written assessment questions. The participants, who completed the course in a live traditional laboratory setting, as well as those who completed it in a virtual aided setting, did well as shown in their final course mark. In both instances, course assessments demonstrated student satisfaction with the course and instructor. The results of the study imply that a student taught in a virtual setting does not differ much in terms of academic performance, compared to those students who were taught in a traditional classroom.

Correspondingly, the study “Student perceptions of online and in-person microbiology laboratory experiences in undergraduate medical education” was conducted to understand the perceptions of students regarding the online and in-person microbiology laboratory learning experiences. A total of 164 first-year medical students took part in the newly constructed online laboratories, whereas 83 second-year medical students continued to use in-person laboratories. An online survey was used to get feedback from students about their lab experience. And the results showed that students who attended the laboratory in person were more likely to indicate a tactile learning style whereas students who learned the content online preferred a visual learning style. On the other hand, students felt that the online microbiology laboratory was more convenient for their schedules when compared to the in-person laboratory. Therefore, the researchers concluded that students are enthusiastic about digital online laboratory activities however, the vast majority of students still want a combination of online and in-person, hands-on laboratory activities. These findings will aid in the customization of microbiology curricula to meet both student and university demands, as well as further research into student perceptions of the laboratory experience.

Likewise, the research “Students’ perception of animal or virtual laboratory in physiology practical classes in PBL medical hybrid curriculum” by de Toledo Durand et. al. (2019), investigates the efficiency of the problem-based learning hybrid curriculum by comparing students' impressions of actual animal handling to the virtual sample in physiological sciences. Medical students from the University of Ribeirão Preto were divided into 3 separate groups as they participated in animal or virtual physiology classes or both. The participants were asked to

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complete a 5-point Likert questionnaire about knowledge acquisition/motivation, the importance of PBL learning goals, gained skills, need for animal use, academic formation, learning impairment, and alternative approaches. The number of participants came to a total of 350 students were included (108 participated in virtual classes, 120 in practical animal laboratory classes, and 122 in both approaches). The majority agreed that the two strategies increased their information acquisition/motivation while also assisting in the reinforcement of lesson goals and skill learning. The cohort that had exposure to both methodologies, on the other hand, preferred the actual animal laboratory. Students agree that using animals is necessary and that it did not interfere with their learning. Their feelings on academic preparation without animal laboratory classes, on the other hand, were mixed, as was whether or not this strategy prompted them to seek out alternate alternatives. It is concluded in this study that the students prefer the handling of actual animals and conducting activities in an actual laboratory rather than a virtual one. They have cited it as “not as effective as animal use”, however, these virtual activities are successful strategies for physiology learning that can be used in practical classes under the PBL medical hybrid curriculum.

On the contrary, the study “Design and students' perceptions of a virtually facilitated outpatient pharmacy practice laboratory course” by Amber et. al. (2019), examined how open student pharmacists were to taking a virtual outpatient pharmacy practice laboratory course. For a first-year laboratory course, a new course design was created that used Zoom, an internet-based video and chat conference room, to communicate across two campuses. Each laboratory session required physical attendance on campus as well as a Zoom connection. At the beginning and end of the course, students voluntarily and anonymously completed a survey to assess course design and its influence on student learning. A total of 159 participants were assessed, where 77 students completed the pre-survey while 82 students completed the post-survey. Students agreed or strongly agreed that virtual facilitation did not hinder learning and disagreed or strongly disagreed that a facilitator needs to be physically present to simplify learning. Students concluded there is no difference in virtual or in-person facilitator communication. While students agreed the experience enabled the development of problem-solving skills and fostered self-awareness and responsibility for self-learning, this was not statistically significant. These findings shed light on how students feel about a laboratory course that is remotely facilitated. This could be a viable alternative to live facilitation while still allowing students to build problem-solving skills, self-awareness, and self-learning responsibilities. Virtual laboratory facilitation could be an innovative course design for schools and colleges of pharmacy.

APPENDIX E**Research Instrument***Appendix E.1 Questionnaire*

**Perception and Attitude of Third and Fourth Year Pharmacy Students
towards Traditional and Virtual Laboratories**

Sample Questionnaire

Part I.

DEMOGRAPHIC OF PARTICIPANTS

Name (Optional): _____

Email address (Optional): _____

Gender: _____

Year and section: _____

Age: _____

Instruction: Read carefully each item before answering and submitting your answer. Mark only the best option in each item. Thank you!

(Panuto: Basahin at unawaing maigi ang bawat tanong bago isumite ang mga datos. Markahan lamang ang pinaka-angkop na sagot. Salamat!)

Categories:

1-Strongly Disagree 2-Disagree 3-Agree 4-Strongly Agree

Part II.

TRADITIONAL LABORATORIES

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
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	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
I. EFFECTIVENESS				
A. Cost friendly				
1. During the face-to-face laboratory, less money is spent on buying PPEs (e.g. gloves, hairnet, and mask). <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas kaunti ang nagagastos sa pagbili ng mga PPE (hal. gloves, hairnet, and mask.)</i>				
2. During the face-to-face laboratory, less money is spent on buying materials (e.g. test tube, white mantle, glass slide, etc.)). <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas kakaunti ang nagagastos sa pagbili ng mga materyales (hal. test tube, white mantle, glass slide, atbp.))</i>				
3. During the face-to-face laboratory, less money is spent in acquiring printed handouts and books required. <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas kakaunti ang nagagastos sa pagbili ng mga kinakailangang printed handouts at libro.)</i>				
4. The face-to-face laboratory is worth the fee based on the services given. <i>(Sulit ang bayad sa face-to-face laboratory base sa serbisyong natatanggap.)</i>				
5. During the face-to-face laboratory, the cost of materials can be easily shared with groupmates. <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, higit na madali ang paghahati ng mga gastusin sa mga kagrupo.)</i>				
6. During the face-to-face laboratory, there is no need to				

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<p>spend money on public transport.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, hindi na kailangan gumastos para sa transportasyon.)</i></p>				
<p>7. During the face-to-face laboratory, there is no need to spend money on snacks.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, hindi na kailangan gumastos para sa baon o meryenda.)</i></p>				
<p>8. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to save more money by not having the risk of breaking any apparatus.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas nakakatipid ng pera sa pamamagitan ng hindi pagkakaroon ng panganib na masira ang anumang kagamitan.)</i></p>				
<p>9. During the face-to-face laboratory, less money will be utilized for acquiring chemicals since it is readily available in the said area.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas nakakatipid ng pera sa mga kemikal sapagkat matatagpuan na mismo ito sa laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>10. During the face-to-face laboratory, there is no need to purchase a laboratory module.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, hindi na kailangang bumili pa ng laboratory module.)</i></p>				
<p>11. During the face-to-face laboratory, there is no need to pay a locker fee for the storage of laboratory materials.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, hindi na kailangang magbayad para sa locker na nagsisilbing taguan ng mga</i></p>				

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<i>kagamitang panglaboratoryo.)</i>				
B. Learning delivery				
<p>1. Face-to-face laboratory provides better learning modes (individual and group activities like an essay, research, etc.).</p> <p><i>(Ang face-to-face laboratory ay nakakapagbigay ng mas mahusay na mga learning modes (indibidwal at pangkatang gawain tulad ng sanaysay, pananaliksik, atbp.)</i></p>				
<p>2. During the face-to-face laboratory, lessons are being understood easier.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory ay mas madaling nauunawaan ang mga aralin.)</i></p>				
<p>3. During the face-to-face laboratory, scientific concepts are better explained with the help of demonstration from professors.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas naipaliliwanag ang mga konseptong pang-aham dahil ito ay naisasagawa ng mga propesor sa harapan ng mga estudyante.)</i></p>				
<p>4. During the face-to-face laboratory, instructions and procedures are better explained.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas naipaliliwanag ng mabuti ang mga panuto at proseso.)</i></p>				
<p>5. During the face-to-face laboratory, proper disposal of waste material (e.g. carcasses, organic and inorganic chemicals, and syringes, etc.) is easily learned.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling natututunan ang tamang pagtatapon ng mga basura (hal.</i></p>				

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<i>carcasses, organic and inorganic chemicals, and syringes atbp.))</i>				
<p>6. During the face-to-face laboratory, there is better visualization and learning of chemical reactions because of first-hand experience in conducting experiments.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas natututunan nang maayos ang mga chemical reactions dahil mismong nararanasan ang pagsasagawa ng mga gawain patungkol dito.)</i></p>				
<p>7. During a face-to-face laboratory, the library can be used as a study area.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, magagamit ang silid-aklatan upang makapag-aral.)</i></p>				
<p>8. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to ask the teacher and friends to explain concepts difficult to understand.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling natatanong ang mga guro at mga kaibigan tungkol sa mga konseptong mahirap unawain.)</i></p>				
<p>9. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to concentrate.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling makapagpokus nang mabuti.)</i></p>				
<p>10. After completing laboratory assignments during the face-to-face laboratory, it is easy to do good on lectures, quizzes & exams.</p> <p><i>(Pagkatapos makumpleto ang mga takdang-aralin noong face-to-face laboratory ay mas napapadali ang pakikinig</i></p>				

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<i>sa lektyur at pagsagot sa pagsusulit.)</i>				
<p>11. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to understand the purpose of the lab experiment.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling maunawaan ang layunin ng mga eksperimentong panglaboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>12. During the face-to-face laboratory, learning is easier due to the simulations.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling matutunan ang mga aralin dahil sa mga simulations.)</i></p>				
<p>13. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to improve practical laboratory skills.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas nahahasa ang praktikal na kasanayan sa laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>14. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to familiarize with theories.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling natututunan ang mga teorya.)</i></p>				
<p>15. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to grasp how to experiment.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas nauunawaan kung paano gawin ang eksperimento.)</i></p>				
<p>16. During the face-to-face laboratory, experiments are performed fast and accurately at the same time.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas naisasagawa nang mabilis at wasto ang mga gawain.)</i></p>				
17. During the face-to-face laboratory, handling of				

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<p>equipments can be done independently.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face na laboratoryo, ang paggamit ng mga kagamitan ay naisasagawa ng mag-isa.)</i></p>				
C. Providing manual dexterity				
<p>1. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to learn procedures that need eye and hand coordination.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling natututunan ang mga Gawain na nangangailangan ng koordinasyon ng mata at kamay.)</i></p>				
<p>2. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to perform skills that need eye and hand coordination like trituration and titration.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling naisasagawa ang mga gawaing nangangailangan ng koordinasyon ng mata at kamay gaya ng trituration at titration.)</i></p>				
<p>3. During the face-to-face laboratory, tasks like trituration and titration are performed with confidence.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, ang mga Gawain gaya ng trituration at titration ay naisasagawa ng may kumpiyansa.)</i></p>				
<p>4. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to demonstrate skill during experiments.</p> <p><i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling naipapakita ang kasanayan sa pag-eksperimento.)</i></p>				
<p>5. During the face-to-face laboratory, small quantities of chemicals can be easily measured precisely.</p>				

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<i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling nasusukat nang tiyak, maging ang kemikal na may maliliit na dami.)</i>				
6. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to manipulate laboratory instruments. <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling nagagamit nang wasto ang mga kagamitan sa laboratoryo.)</i>				
D. Providing proper technique in handling tools and equipment				
1. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to learn proper laboratory techniques. <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madali natututunan ang mga tamang pamamaraan na pang laboratoryo.)</i>				
2. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to retain proper techniques in handling tools and equipment. <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling maisaulo ang tamang pamamaraan/teknik sa paghawak ng kasangkapan/kagamitan.)</i>				
3. During the face-to-face laboratory, handling of tools and equipment is done with proper etiquette. <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas nasusunod ang wastong etiquette sa paggamit ng mga kasangkapan at kagamitan.)</i>				
4. During the face-to-face laboratory, accurate taring of apparatuses can be done. <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, nagagawang tiyak ang pag-tare ng mga apparatus.)</i>				
5. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to practice proper sanitation of workspace and equipment.				

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<i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling sanayin ang tamang paglilinis ng workspace at kagamitan.)</i>				
6. During the face-to-face laboratory, proper handling of miscellaneous laboratory devices like the microscope can be practiced. <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, nagagawang magsanay na gamitin nang wasto ang miscellaneous na kagamitan sa laboratory tulad ng microscope.)</i>				
7. The skills acquired during face-to-face laboratory can be used to handle equipment in the actual pharmacy field. <i>(Ang mga kasanayang natutunan noong face-to-face laboratory, ay magagamit sa aktwal na larangan ng parmasiya.)</i>				
8. During the face-to-face laboratory, it is easier to yield accurate results by using equipment in experiments. <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling makakuha ng eksaktong resulta gamit and mga kagamitan sa pag-eksperimento.)</i>				
9. During the face-to-face laboratory, mistakes are seldom made during experiments. <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madalang na nagagawa ang pagkakamali sa mga eksperimento.)</i>				
II. CONVENIENCE				
A. Facilities				
1. Face-to-face laboratory is more comfortable to experiment in. <i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo ay mas kumportableng</i>				

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<i>mag-eksperimento.)</i>				
2. Face-to-face laboratory feels more secure. <i>(Mas ligtas sa pakiramdam magsagawa ng eksperimento sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i>				
3. Experiments can be performed with fewer distractions in the face-to-face laboratory. <i>(Maaaring isagawa ang mga eksperimento nang may mas kaunting mga distraksyon sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i>				
4. Chemicals or reagents readily available in the face-to-face laboratory. <i>(Ang mga kemikal o reagents ay nakahandang magamit sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i>				
5. Performing experiments in a face-to-face laboratory is easier because necessities are readily available (e.g. Wifi, computer, cellphone, etc.). <i>(Ang pagsasagawa ng mga eksperimento sa face-to-face na laboratoryo ay mas madali dahil ang mga pangangailangan ay nakahanda (hal. wifi, computer, cellphone, atbp.))</i>				
6. In a face-to-face laboratory, proper and safe waste disposal of materials after an experiment is evident. <i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo, maaari kong ligtas na itapon ang mga basura pagkatapos ng isang eksperimento.)</i>				
7. In a face-to-face laboratory, there is less frequency of accidents/injuries. <i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo, nakakaranas ako ng mas</i>				

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<i>kaunting dalas na mga aksidente/pinsala.)</i>				
8. Learning is better due to the aesthetically pleasing environment in the face-to-face laboratory. <i>(Mas maayos ang pag-aaral dahil sa estetikong kapaligiran sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i>				
9. Students perform experiments without worrying about hurting anybody in the face-to-face laboratory. <i>(Nakagagawa ang mga estudyante ng mga eksperimento nang hindi nababahala na masaktan ang sinuman sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i>				
10. Face-to-face laboratory provides proper ventilation for the chemicals being used during experiments. <i>(Ang face-to-face na laboratoryo ay nagbibigay ng wastong bentilasyon para sa mga kemikal na ginagamit sa panahon ng mga eksperimento.)</i>				
11. Face-to-face laboratory provides a well-structured facility for me to perform experiments well. <i>(Ang face-to-face na laboratoryo ay nagbibigay ng isang maayos na pasilidad para sa akin upang maisagawa ko nang maayos ang mga eksperimento.)</i>				
B. Accessibility of devices, materials, and instruments used				
1. It is easier to obtain complete PPE (lab gown, disposable masks, hairnet, and safety eyeglasses) in the face-to-face laboratory. <i>(Mas madaling makakuha ng kumpletong PPE (lab gown, disposable masks, hairnet, at safety eyeglasses) sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i>				

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<p>2. It is easier to perform experiments because instruments and devices are readily available in the face-to-face laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas madaling magsagawa ng mga eksperimento sa face-to-face na laboratory dahil ang mga instrumento at kagamitan ay madaling makuha.)</i></p>				
<p>3. It is easier to acquire necessary learning materials (e.g. laboratory manual and handouts) in the face-to-face laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas madaling kumuha ng mga kinakailangang materyales sa pag-aaral (hal. laboratory manual at handout) sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>4. In a face-to-face laboratory, there are readily available materials therefore students do not need to purchase any materials.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo, mayroon nang nakahandang materyales na magagamit, samakatuwid, hindi na kailangang bumili ng anumang mga materyales.)</i></p>				
<p>5. Face to-face laboratory provides a faster way to finish experiments due to instruments being available.</p> <p><i>(Nagbibigay ang face-to-face na laboratoryo ng mas mabilis na paraan upang tapusin ang mga eksperimento dahil sa mga instrumento na magagamit.)</i></p>				
<p>6. Face-to-face laboratory provides high-end apparatus available for students to get accurate results.</p> <p><i>(Ang face-to-face na laboratoryo ay nagbibigay ng magandang klaseng kagamitan na magagamit ng mga mag-aaral upang makakuha ng mga tamang resulta.)</i></p>				

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<p>7. Face-to-face laboratory makes it possible to attain the preferred experiment results due to the availability of devices.</p> <p><i>(Ginagawang posible ng face-to-face na laboratoryo na makuha ang gustong resulta ng eksperimento dahil sa pagkakaroon ng mga kagamitan.)</i></p>				
<p>8. Printing out the required modules is trouble-free in a face-to-face laboratory</p> <p><i>(Mas madaling makapag-print ng mga kinakailangang modyul noong face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
C. Getting assistance from professors				
<p>1. In a face-to-face laboratory the professor is always available at the time of the class.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo ang mga propesor ay laging naroon sa oras ng klase.)</i></p>				
<p>2. In a face-to-face laboratory it is easier to ask the professors for assistance if the group encountered a problem when experimenting in which laboratory setting.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo ay mas madaling humingi ng tulong sa mga propesor kung ang grupo ay nakatagpo ng isang problema habang nag-eeksperimento.)</i></p>				
<p>3. In face-to-face laboratory students are not scared to perform a technical activity (e.g. trituration, levigation, etc.) because they know that the professor is ready to assist them.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo ay hindi natatakot ang mga estudyante na magsagawa ng teknikal na aktibidad (hal. trituration, levigation, atbp.) dahil alam nila na ang</i></p>				

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<i>propesor ay handing tumulong sa kanila.)</i>				
<p>4. Students are more confident in the face-to-face laboratory because they know that the professor is knowledgeable about the protocols once there is an emergency.</p> <p><i>(Panatag ang loob ng mga estudyante noong face-to-face na laboratoryo dahil alam nilang may sapat na kaalaman ang mga propesor sa pagresponde kung sakaling magkaroon ng hindi inaasahang mga pangyayari.)</i></p>				
<p>5. In face-to-face laboratory understanding lessons may depend on the professor's guidance.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo ay mas naiintindihan ang mga aralin nang may kalinawan dahil sa patnubay ng mga propesor.)</i></p>				
<p>6. It is faster to get a professor's reply about an inquiry in the face-to-face laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas mabilis na makakuha ng tugon ng isang propesor tungkol sa isang pagtatanong sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>7. In a face-to-face laboratory it is easier to approach professors regarding personal matters that refrain a student from being present during the laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo mas madaling lumapit sa mga propesor tungkol sa mga personal nabagay na pumipigil sa isang estudyante na dumalo sa klase sa laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>8. It is easier to approach a professor regarding your progress in the experiment in a face-to-face laboratory.</p>				

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<p><i>(Mas madaling lapitan ang propesor ukol sa iyong progreso sa ginagawang eksperimento sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>9. Face-to-face laboratory allows students to not have to suffer silently when confused about a laboratory exercise.</p> <p><i>(Pinahihintulutan ako ng face-to-face na laboratoryo na hindi magdusa nang tahimik kapag nalilito tungkol sa isang eksperimentong panglaboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>D. Creating an output</p>				
<p>1. It is easier to come up with a way on how to execute the plan in making an output during the face-to-face laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas madaling makabuo ng paraan kung paano isasagawa ang plano sa paggawa ng output sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>2. It is easier to troubleshoot any inaccuracies when implementing the plan for making an output during the face-to-face laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas madaling solusyunan ang mga pagkakamali sa gawain sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>3. Face-to-face laboratory makes it easier to obtain results in experiments due to the instruments being readily available.</p> <p><i>(Pinapadali ng face-to-face na laboratoryo ang pagkuha ng mga resulta sa mga eksperimento.)</i></p>				
<p>4. In face-to-face laboratory creating an output faster.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo, mas mabilis na nakakagawa ng output.)</i></p>				

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<p>5. In face-to-face laboratory students can get immediate feedback about their output.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo nakakakuha ang mga estudyante ng agarang tugon tungkol sa kanilang output.)</i></p>				
<p>6. In face-to-face laboratory students can create accurate output easily because they are able to make early adjustments based on the criteria given.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo, ang mga mag-aaral ay kayang makagawa ng output na nakabase sa pamantayan kaya naman nagagawa nila ng mas wasto ang kanilang mga output.)</i></p>				
<p>7. The possibility of acquiring better grades with output may be due to the higher accuracy of process done in face-to-face laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas mataas ang posibilidad na makakuha nang mahusay na marka sa output na sanhi ng tamang prosesong face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>8. Face-to-face laboratory setting makes it much easier to understand the process of making an output due to the comprehensive discussion of the professors.</p> <p><i>(Ginagawang mas madaling maunawaan ng face-to-face na setting ng laboratoryo ang prosesong paggawa ng output dahil sa komprehensibong talakayan ng mga propesor.)</i></p>				
<p>9. In the face-to-face laboratory setting it is easier to manage information in group to create better output.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo, mas madaling pamahalaan ang mga impormasyon nang pangkatan para</i></p>				

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<i>makalikha ng mas maayos na output.)</i>				
10. Outputs are made with confidence due to less confusion regarding the procedure taught by the professor in a face-to-face laboratory. <i>(Mas may kumpyansa sa mga output na ginawa dahil mas komprehensibo ang ginawang talakayan ng propesor sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i>				
11. It is easy to obtain experimental results in a face-to-face laboratory. <i>(Madaling makakuha ng mga resulta sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i>				
E. Being in a group				
1. In a face-to-face laboratory it is easier to plan for the experiment as a group. <i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo mas madaling magplano para sa eksperimento bilang isang grupo.)</i>				
2. Brainstorming is easier in the face-to-face laboratory. <i>(Mas madali ang palitan ng ideya sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i>				
3. Face-to-face laboratory setting helps make it easier to provide ideas and receive feedback from groupmates about individual performance. <i>(Nakakatulong ang face-to-face na setting ng laboratoryo na gawing mas madali ang pagbibigay ng mga ideya at pagtanggap ng tugon mula sa mga kagrupo tungkol sa indibidwal na gawain.)</i>				
4. Face-to-face laboratory setting helps make it easier to understand the task given with the help of my groupmates.				

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<p><i>(Ang face-to-face na laboratoryo ay nakakatulong na mas madaling maintitindihan ang gawain dahil sa tulong ng mga kagrupo.)</i></p>				
<p>5. Face-to-face laboratory setting helps make it easier to simplify tasks as a group.</p> <p><i>(Nakakatulong ang face-to-face na setting ng laboratoryo na gawing mas madali ang mga gawain bilang isang grupo.)</i></p>				
<p>6. Face-to-face laboratory setting helps me to develop strong communication skills due to participating in a group.</p> <p><i>(Ang face-to-face na setting ng laboratoryo ay tumutulong sa akin na magkaroon ng malakas na kasanayan sa komunikasyon dahil sa pakikilahok sa isang grupo.)</i></p>				
<p>7. In face-to-face laboratory tasks are performed faster in a group.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo mas mabilis na natatapos ang mga gawain kapag nasa isang grupo.)</i></p>				
<p>8. Groupmates do not delay results for the experiment in a face-to-face laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Hindi naaantala ng mga kagrupo ang resulta ng eksperimento sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>9. In a face-to-face laboratory working with a group is not hassle.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo hindi abala ang pagsasagawa ng gawain bilang isang grupo.)</i></p>				
<p>10. Everyone takes part in bringing the outcome in the</p>				

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<p>face-to-face laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Ang bawat isa ay nakikibahagi sa paggawa ng resulta sa face-to-face setting ng laboratory.)</i></p>				
F. Organizing own time				
<p>1. In the face-to-face laboratory I am much more organized in terms of prioritizing things.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo ako ay mas organisado sa mga tuntunin ng pagbibigay-priyoridad sa mga bagay.)</i></p>				
<p>2. In a face-to-face laboratory I can manage my time well.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratoryo gamay ko ang aking oras.)</i></p>				
<p>3. Face-to-face laboratory setting allows me to have enough time to review even after doing experiments.</p> <p><i>(Ang face-to-face na setting ng laboratoryo ay nagbibigay-daan sa akin na magkaroon ng sapat na oras upang masuring muli kahit na matapos na ang paggawa ng mga eksperimento.)</i></p>				
<p>4. In a face-to-face laboratory setting I experience less stress because of easier time management.</p> <p><i>(Sa face-to-face na setting ng laboratoryo na kakaranas ako ng mas kaunting stress dahil sa mas madaling pamamahala ng oras.)</i></p>				
<p>5. Face-to-face laboratory setting allows me to have a better work-life balance.</p> <p><i>(Nagbibigay-daan sa akin ang face-to-face na setting ng laboratoryo na magkaroon ng mas magandang balance sa gawain-buhay.)</i></p>				

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6. In a face-to-face laboratory setting I procrastinate less. <i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratory nagagawa kong hindi magpaliban ng mga gawain.)</i>				
7. In the face-to-face laboratory setting I am less overwhelmed with the tasks given. <i>(Sa face-to-face na setting ng laboratoryo hindi ako gaanong na babahala sa mga gawaing ibinigay.)</i>				
8. I can manage my sleep schedule better in the face-to-face laboratory setting. <i>(Mas napapamahalaan ko ang aking iskedyul ng pagtulog sa tradisyonal na setting ng laboratoryo.)</i>				
9. I can study well in the face-to-face laboratory. <i>(Mas nakakapag-aral ako ng mabuti sa face-to-face na laboratoryo.)</i>				
10. In a face-to-face laboratory setting I finish all or most requirements needed on time. <i>(Sa face-to-face na laboratory nagagawa kong tapusin ang lahat o karamihan ng mga kinakailangan sa takdang-oras.)</i>				

VIRTUAL LABORATORIES

	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Agree (3)	Strongly Agree (4)
I. EFFECTIVENESS				
A. Cost friendly				
1. During the virtual laboratory, less money is spent on buying PPEs (e.g. gloves, hairnet, and mask).				

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<p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas kaunting pera ang magagastos sa pagbili ng mga PPE (hal. gloves, hairnet, and mask.))</i></p>				
<p>2. During the virtual laboratory, less money is spent on buying materials (e.g. test tube, white mantle, glass slide, etc.).</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas kaunting pera ang magagastos sa pagbili ng mga materyales (hal. test tube, white mantle, glass slide, atbp.))</i></p>				
<p>3. During the virtual laboratory, less money is spent in acquiring printed handouts and books required.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas kaunting pera ang magagastos sa pagbili ng mga kinakailangang printed handouts at libro.)</i></p>				
<p>4. The virtual laboratory is worth the fee based on the services given.</p> <p><i>(Sulit and bayad sa virtual laboratory base sa serbisyong natatanggap.)</i></p>				
<p>5. During the virtual laboratory, the cost of materials can be easily shared with groupmates.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas napapadali ang paghati ng mga gastusin sa mga kagrupo.)</i></p>				
<p>6. During the virtual laboratory, there is no need to spend money on public transport.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, hindi na kailangan gumastos para sa transportasyon.)</i></p>				
<p>7. During the virtual laboratory, there is no need to spend</p>				

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<p>money on snacks.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, hindi na kailangan gumastos para sa baon o meryenda.)</i></p>				
<p>8. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to save more money by not having the risk of breaking any apparatus.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas makakatipid ng pera sa pamamagitan ng hindi pagkakaroon ng panganib na masira ang anumang kagamitan.)</i></p>				
<p>9. During the virtual laboratory, less money will be utilized for acquiring chemicals since it is readily available in the said area.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas nakakatipid ng pera sa paggamit ng mga kemikal sapagkat matatagpuan na ito sa laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>10. During the virtual laboratory, there is no need to purchase a laboratory module.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, hindi na kailangang bumili pa ng modyul na panglaboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>11. During the virtual laboratory, there is no need to pay a locker fee for the storage of laboratory materials.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, hindi na kailangang magbayad para sa locker na nagsisilbing taguan ng mga kagamitang panglaboratoryo.)</i></p>				
B. Learning delivery				
<p>1. Virtual laboratory provides better learning modes (individual and group activities like an essay, research, etc.).</p>				

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<p><i>(Ang virtual laboratory ay nakakapagbigay ng mas mahusay na mga learning modes (indibidwal at pangkatang gawain tulad ng sanaysay, pananaliksik, atbp..))</i></p>				
<p>2. During the virtual laboratory, lessons are being understood easier.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory ay mas nauunawaang mabuti ang mga aralin.)</i></p>				
<p>3. During the virtual laboratory, scientific concepts are better explained with the help of demonstration from professors.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas naipaliliwanag ang mga konseptong pang-agham dahil ito ay naisasagawa ng mga propesor sa harapan ng mga estudyante.)</i></p>				
<p>4. During the virtual laboratory, instructions and procedures are better explained.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas naipaliliwanag nang mabuti ang mga panuto at proseso.)</i></p>				
<p>5. During the virtual laboratory, proper disposal of waste material (e.g. carcasses, organic and inorganic chemicals, and syringes, etc.) is easily learned.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madaling natututunan ang tamang pagtatapon ng mga basura (hal. carcasses, organic and inorganic chemicals, and syringes atbp..))</i></p>				
<p>6. During the virtual laboratory, there is better visualization on learning chemical reactions because of first-hand experience in conducting experiments.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas natututunan nang maayos</i></p>				

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<i>ang mga chemical reactions dahil mismong nararanasan ang pagsasagawa ng mga gawaing patungkol dito.)</i>				
7. During the virtual laboratory, the library can be used as a study area. <i>(Sa virtual laboratory, magagamit ang silid-aklatan upang makapag-aral.)</i>				
8. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to ask the teachers and friends to better explain the concepts that are difficult to understand. <i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madaling natatanong ang mga guro at kaibigan tungkol sa mga konseptong mahirap unawain.)</i>				
9. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to concentrate. <i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madaling makapag-focus nang mabuti.)</i>				
10. After completing laboratory assignments during the virtual laboratory, it is easy to listen on lectures and answer the exams. <i>(Pagkatapos makumpleto ang mga takdang-aralin sa virtual laboratory ay mas napapadali ang pakikinig sa lecture at pagsagot sa pagsusulit.)</i>				
11. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to understand the purpose of the lab experiment. <i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madaling maunawaan ang layunin ng eksperimentong panglaboratoryo.)</i>				
12. During a virtual laboratory, learning is easier due to the simulations.				

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<i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas higit na natutunan ang mga aralin dahil sa mga simulations.)</i>				
13. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to improve practical laboratory skills. <i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas nahahasa ang praktikal na kasanayan sa laboratoryo.)</i>				
14. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to familiarize with theories. <i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madaling natututunan ang mga teorya.)</i>				
15. During the virtual laboratory, experiments are performed fast and accurately at the same time. <i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas naisasagawa nang mabilis at wasto ang mga gawain.)</i>				
16. During a virtual laboratory, it is easier to grasp how to experiment. <i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas nauunawaan kung paano gawin ang eksperimento.)</i>				
17. During a virtual laboratory, handling of equipments can be done independently. <i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo, ang paggamit ng mga kagamitan ay naisasagawa ng mag-isa</i>				
C. Providing manual dexterity				
1. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to learn procedures that need eye and hand coordination. <i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madaling natututunan ang mga gawain na nangangailangan ng koordinasyon ng</i>				

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<i>mata at kamay.)</i>				
<p>2. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to perform skills that need eye and hand coordination like trituration and titration.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madaling naisasagawa ang mga gawaing nangangailangan ng koordinasyon ng mata at kamay gaya ng trituration at titration.)</i></p>				
<p>3. During the virtual laboratory, tasks like trituration and titration are performed with confidence.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, ang mga gawain gaya ng trituration at titration ay naisasagawa ng may kumpiyansa.)</i></p>				
<p>4. During a virtual laboratory, it is easier to demonstrate skill during experiments.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madaling naipapakita ang kasanayan sa pag-eksperimento.)</i></p>				
<p>5. During a virtual laboratory, small quantities of chemicals can be easily measured precisely.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madaling nasusukat nang tiyak, maging ang kemikal na may maliliit na dami.)</i></p>				
<p>6. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to manipulate laboratory instruments.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madaling nagagamit nang wasto ang mga kagamitan sa laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
D. Providing proper technique in handling tools and equipment				
<p>1. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to learn proper laboratory techniques.</p>				

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<p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madali natututunan ang mga tamang pamamaraan na pang laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>2. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to retain proper techniques in handling tools and equipment.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madaling maisaulo ang mga tamang pamamaraan/teknik na pang laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>3. During the virtual laboratory, handling of tools and equipment is done with proper etiquette.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas nasusunod ang wastong etiquette sa paggamit ng mga kasangkapan at kagamitan.)</i></p>				
<p>4. During the virtual laboratory, accurate taring of apparatuses can be done.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, nagagawang tiyak ang pag-tare ng mga apparatus sa laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>5. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to practice proper sanitation of workspace and equipment.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madaling sanayin ang tamang paglilinis ng workspace at kagamitan.)</i></p>				
<p>6. During the virtual laboratory, proper handling of miscellaneous laboratory devices like the microscope can be practiced.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual laboratory, nagagawang magsanay na gamitin nang wasto ang miscellaneous na kagamitan sa laboratoryo tulad ng microscope.)</i></p>				
<p>7. The skills acquired during virtual laboratory can be used to handle equipment in the actual pharmacy field.</p>				

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<i>(Ang mga kasanayang natutunan sa virtual laboratory, ay magagamit sa aktwal na larangan ng Parmasiya.)</i>				
8. During the virtual laboratory, it is easier to yield accurate results by using equipment in experiments. <i>(Noong face-to-face laboratory, mas madaling makakuha ng eksaktong resulta gamit and mga kagamitan sa pag-eksperimento.)</i>				
9. During the virtual laboratory, mistakes are seldom made during experiments. <i>(Sa virtual laboratory, mas madalang na nagagawa ang pagkakamali sa mga eksperimento.)</i>				
II. CONVENIENCE				
A. Facilities				
1. Virtual laboratory is more comfortable to experiment in. <i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo ay mas komportableng mag-eksperimento.)</i>				
2. Virtual laboratory feels more secure. <i>(Mas ligtas sa pakiramdam ang virtual na laboratoryo sa pag-eksperimento.)</i>				
3. Experiments can be performed with fewer distractions in a virtual laboratory. <i>(Maaaring isagawa ang mga eksperimento nang may mas kaunting mga distractions sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i>				
4. Chemicals are readily available in a virtual laboratory. <i>(Ang mga kemikal ay nakahandang magamit sa virtual na</i>				

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<i>laboratoryo.)</i>				
<p>5. Performing experiments in a virtual laboratory is easier because I have the necessities (e.g. Wifi, computer, cellphone, etc.).</p> <p><i>(Ang pagsasagawa ng mga eksperimento sa virtual na laboratoryo ay mas madali dahil ang mga pangangailangan ay nakahanda (hal. Wifi, computer, cellphone, atbp.)</i></p>				
<p>6. In a virtual laboratory, proper waste disposal of materials after an experiment is evident.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo, ang wastong pagtatapon ng mga basura pagkatapos ng isang eksperimento ay naisasagawa.)</i></p>				
<p>7. In a virtual laboratory, there is less frequency of accidents/injuries.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo, nakakaranas ng mas kaunting dalas ng mgaaksidente/pinsala.)</i></p>				
<p>8. Learning is better due to the aesthetically pleasing environment in a virtual laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas maayos ang pag-aaral dahil sa estetikong kapaligiran sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>9. Students perform experiments without worrying about hurting anybody in a virtual laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Nakakagawa ang mga estudyante ng mga eksperimento nang hindi nababahala na masaktan ang sinuman sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>10. Virtual laboratory provides proper ventilation for the chemicals being used during experiments.</p>				

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<p><i>(Ang virtual na laboratoryo ay nagbibigay ng wastong bentilasyon para sa mga kemikal na ginagamit ko sa panahon ng mga eksperimento.)</i></p>				
<p>11. Virtual laboratory provides a well-structured facility for me to perform experiments well.</p> <p><i>(Ang virtual na laboratoryo ay nagbibigay ng isang maayos na pasilidad upang maisagawa nang maayos ang mga eksperimento.)</i></p>				
<p>B. Accessibility of devices, materials, and instruments used</p>				
<p>1. It is easier to obtain complete PPE (lab gown, disposable masks, hairnet, and safety eyeglasses) in a virtual laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas madaling makakuha ng kumpletong PPE (lab gown, disposable masks, hairnet, at safety eyeglasses) sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>2. It is easier to perform experiments because instruments are readily available in the virtual laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas madaling magsagawa ng mga eksperimento sa virtual na laboratory dahil ang mga instrumento at kagamitan ay madaling makuha.)</i></p>				
<p>3. It is easier to acquire necessary learning materials (e.g. laboratory manual and handouts) in a virtual laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas madaling kumuha ng mga kinakailangang materyales sa pag-aaral (hal. laboratory manual at handout) sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>4. In a virtual laboratory, there are readily available materials, therefore, students do not need to purchase any</p>				

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<p>materials.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo, mayroon nakahandang magagamit na mga materyales, samakatuwid, hindi na kailangang bumili ng anumang mga materyales.)</i></p>				
<p>5. Virtual laboratory provides a faster way to finish experiments due to instruments being available.</p> <p><i>(Nagbibigay ang virtual na laboratoryo ng mas mabilis na paraan upang tapusin ang mga eksperimento dahil sa mga instrument na magagamit.)</i></p>				
<p>6. Virtual laboratory provides high-end apparatus available for students to get accurate results.</p> <p><i>(Ang virtual na laboratoryo ay nagbibigay ng magandang klaseng kagamitan na magagamit ng mga mag-aaral upang makakuha ng mga eksaktong resulta.)</i></p>				
<p>7. Virtual laboratory makes it possible to attain the preferred experiment results due to the availability of devices.</p> <p><i>(Ginagawang posible ng virtual na laboratoryo na makuha ang hinihinging resulta nang eksperimento dahil sa pagkakaroon ng mga kagamitan.)</i></p>				
<p>8. Printing out the required modules is trouble-free in the virtual laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas madaling makapag-print ng mga kinakailangang modyul sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
C. Getting assistance from professors				
<p>1. In a virtual laboratory the professor is always available at the time of the class.</p>				

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<i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo ang mga propesor ay laging naroon sa oras ng klase.)</i>				
<p>2. In a virtual laboratory it is easier to ask the professors for assistance if the group encountered a problem when experimenting in which laboratory setting.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo ay mas madaling humingi ng tulong sa mga propesor kung ang grupo ay nakatagpo ng isang problema habang nag-eksperimento.)</i></p>				
<p>3. In virtual laboratory students are not scared to perform a technical activity (e.g. trituration, levigation, etc.) because they know that the professor is ready to assist them.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo hindi natatakot gumawa ng mga teknikal na gawain (hal. trituration, titration, inoculation, atpb.) dahil alam mong nariyan ang iyong guro na handang umalalay sa iyo.)</i></p>				
<p>4. Students are more confident in the virtual laboratory because they know that the professor is knowledgeable about the protocols once there is an emergency.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo ay hindi natatakot ang mga estudyante na magsagawa ng teknikal na aktibidad (hal. trituration, levigation, atpb.) dahil alam nila na ang propesor ay handing tumulong sa kanila.)</i></p>				
<p>5. In a virtual laboratory, understanding lessons depends on the professor's guidance.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo mas naiintindihan ang mga aralin nang may kalinawan dahil sa patnubay ng mga propesor.)</i></p>				
<p>6. It is faster to get a professor's reply about an inquiry in</p>				

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<p>a virtual laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas mabilis na makakuha ng tugon sa propesor tungkol sa isang pagtatanong sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>7. In a virtual laboratory it is easier to approach professors regarding personal matters that refrain a student from being present during the experiment.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo mas madaling lumapit sa mga propesor tungkol sa mga personal na bagay na pumipigil sa isang estudyante na dumalo sa loob ng klase habang nag-eksperimento.)</i></p>				
<p>8. It is easier to approach a professor regarding your progress in the experiment in a virtual laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas madaling lapitan ang propesor ukol sa iyong progreso sa ginagawang eksperimento sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>9. Virtual laboratory allows students to not have to suffer silently when confused about a laboratory exercise.</p> <p><i>(Pinahihintulutan ng virtual na laboratoryo na hindi magdusa nang tahimik ang mga estudyante kapag nalilito tungkol sa isang pagsasanay sa laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
D. Creating an output				
<p>1. It is easier to come up with a way on how to execute the plan in making an output during the virtual laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas madaling makabuo ng paraan kung paano isasagawa ang plano sa paggawa ng output sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>2. It is easier to troubleshoot any inaccuracies when</p>				

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<p>implementing the plan for making an output during the virtual laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas madaling solusyunan ang mga pagkakamali sa gawain sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>3. Virtual laboratory makes it easier to obtain results in experiments due to the instruments being readily available.</p> <p><i>(Pinapadali ng virtual na laboratoryo ang pagkuha ng mga resulta sa mga eksperimento.)</i></p>				
<p>4. In a virtual laboratory, creating an output faster.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo, mas mabilis na nakakagawa ng output.)</i></p>				
<p>5. In virtual laboratory students can get immediate feedback about their output.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo nakakakuha ang mga estudyante ng agarang tugon tungkol sa kanilang output.)</i></p>				
<p>6. In virtual laboratory students can create accurate output easily because they are able to make early adjustments based on the criteria given.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo, ang mga mag-aaral ay kayang makagawa ng output na nakabase sa pamantayan kaya naman nagagawa nila ng mas wasto ang kanilang mga output.)</i></p>				
<p>6. The possibility of acquiring better grades with output may be due to the higher accuracy of process done in virtual laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas mataas ang posibilidad na makakuha nang</i></p>				

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<i>mahusay na marka sa output na sanhi ng tamang prosesong virtual na laboratoryo.)</i>				
8. Virtual laboratory setting makes it much easier to understand the process of making an output due to the comprehensive discussion of the professors. <i>(Ginagawang mas madaling maunawaan ng virtual na setting ng laboratoryo ang prosesong paggawa ng output dahil sa komprehensibong talakayan ng mga propesor.)</i>				
9. In the virtual laboratory setting it is easier to manage information in group to create better output. <i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo, mas madaling pamahalaan ang mga impormasyon nang pangkatan para makalikha ng mas maayos na output.)</i>				
10. Outputs are made with confidence due to less confusion regarding the procedure taught by the professor in the virtual laboratory. <i>(Mas may kumpyansa sa output na ginawa dahil mas komprehensibo ang ginawang talakayan ng propesor sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i>				
11. It is easy to obtain experimental results in a virtual laboratory. <i>(Madaling makakuha ng mga resulta sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i>				
E. Being in a group				
1. In a virtual laboratory it is easier to plan for the experiment as a group. <i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo mas madaling magplano para</i>				

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<i>sa eksperimento bilang isang grupo.)</i>				
2. Brainstorming is easier in a virtual laboratory. <i>(Mas madali ang palitan ng mga ideya sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i>				
3. Virtual laboratory setting helps make it easier to provide ideas and receive feedback from groupmates about individual performance. <i>(Nakakatulong ang virtual na setting ng laboratoryo na gawing mas madali ang pagbibigay ng mga ideya at pagtanggap ng tugon mula sa mga kagrupong tungkol sa indibidwal na gawain.)</i>				
4. Virtual laboratory setting helps make it easier to understand the task given with the help of my groupmates. <i>(Ang virtual na laboratoryo ay nakakatulong na mas madaling maintitindihan ang gawain sa tulong ng mga kagrupong.)</i>				
5. Virtual laboratory setting helps make it easier to simplify tasks as a group. <i>(Nakakatulong ang virtual na setting ng laboratoryo na gawing mas madali ang mga gawain bilang isang grupo.)</i>				
6. In virtual laboratory tasks are performed faster in a group. <i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo mas mabilis na natatapos ang mga gawain kapag nasa isang grupo.)</i>				
7. Groupmates do not delay results for the experiment in a virtual laboratory.				

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<i>(Hindi naaantala ng mga kagrupong ang resulta ng eksperimento sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i>				
8. In a virtual laboratory working with a group is not hassle. <i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo hindi abala ang pagsasagawa ng gawain bilang isang grupo.)</i>				
9. Everyone takes part in bringing the outcome to the virtual laboratory. <i>(Ang bawat isa ay nakikibahagi sa paggawa ng resulta sa virtual na setting ng laboratoryo.)</i>				
F. Organizing own time				
1. In a virtual laboratory I am much more organized in terms of prioritizing things. <i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo ako ay mas organisado sa mga tuntunin ng pagbibigay-prioridad sa mga bagay.)</i>				
2. In a virtual laboratory I can manage my time well. <i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo gamay ko ang aking oras.)</i>				
3. Virtual laboratory setting allows me to have enough time to review even after doing experiments. <i>(Ang virtual na setting ng laboratoryo ay nagbibigay-daan sa akin na magkaroon ng sapat na oras upang mag-review kahit na matapos ang paggawa ng mga eksperimento.)</i>				
4. In a virtual laboratory setting I experience less stress because of easier time management. <i>(Sa virtual na setting ng laboratoryo nakakaranas ako ng mas kaunting stress dahil sa mas madaling pamamahala</i>				

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<i>ng oras.)</i>				
<p>5. Virtual laboratory setting allows me to have a better work-life balance.</p> <p><i>(Nagbibigay-daan sa akin ang virtual na setting ng laboratoryo na magkaroon ng mas magandang balanse sa gawain-buhay.)</i></p>				
<p>6. In a virtual laboratory setting I procrastinate less.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo nagagawa kong hindi magpaliban ng mga gawain.)</i></p>				
<p>7. In a virtual laboratory setting I am less overwhelmed with the tasks given.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na setting ng laboratoryo hindi ako gaanong nababahala sa mga gawaing ibinigay.)</i></p>				
<p>8. I can manage my sleep schedule better in a virtual laboratory setting.</p> <p><i>(Mas napapamahalaan ko ang aking iskedyul ng pagtulog sa tradisyonal na setting ng laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>9. I can study well in the virtual laboratory.</p> <p><i>(Mas nakakapag-aral ako ng mabuti sa virtual na laboratoryo.)</i></p>				
<p>10. In a virtual laboratory setting I finish all or most requirements needed on time.</p> <p><i>(Sa virtual na laboratoryo nagagawa kong tapusin ang lahat o karamihan ng mga kinakailangan sa takdang-oras.)</i></p>				

9.0 List of Ten (10) Selected Journals

Barriers to Online Learning in the Time of COVID-19: A National Survey of Medical Students in the Philippines

Baticulon, R. E., Sy, J. J., Alberto, N. R., Baron, M. B., Mabulay, R. E., Rizada, L. G., [...], & Reyes, J.C. (2021). *Barriers to Online Learning in the Time of COVID-19: A National Survey of Medical Students in the Philippines*. Med.Sci.Educ. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40670-021-01231-z>.

Online Distance Learning: Thematic Study on the Challenges Faced by EducareColege Inc. Primary Pupils. Advanced Research in Education, Teaching & Learning

Belgica, C. C., Calugan, J. A., Dumo, J. U., & Simber, L. A. (2020). *Online Distance Learning: Thematic Study on the Challenges Faced by EducareColege Inc. Primary Pupils*. Advanced Research in Education, Teaching & Learning. United Kingdom.

Design and Students' Perceptions of a Virtually Facilitated Outpatient Pharmacy Practice Laboratory Course

Darr, A., Erickson, S., Devine, T., & Tran, T. (2019). *Design and students' perceptions of a virtually facilitated outpatient pharmacy practice laboratory course*. Science Direct. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cptl.2019.03.012>.

Comparison of Pharmacy Students' Performance in a Laboratory Course Delivered Live Versus by Virtual Facilitation

Darr, A., Kyner, M., Fletcher, R., & Yoder, A. (2021). *Comparison of Pharmacy Students' Performance in a Laboratory Course Delivered Live Versus by Virtual Facilitation* [PDF]. American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education. <https://www.ajpe.org/content/ajpe/85/2/8072.full.pdf>.

Students' Perception of Animal or Virtual Laboratory in Physiology Practical Classes in PBL Medical Hybrid Curriculum

De Tuledo Durand, M., Restini, C.B., Wolff, A., Faria, M., Couto, L.B., Bestetti, R.B. (2019, Aug 28). *Students' perception of animal or virtual laboratory in physiology practical*

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classes in PBL medical hybrid curriculum. American Physiological Society Journals.
<https://doi.org/10.1152/advan.00005.2019>.

Online Delivery of Teaching and Laboratory Practices: Continuity of University Programmes during COVID-19 Pandemic

Gamage, K. A., Wijesuriya, D. I., Ekanayake, S. Y., Rennie, A. E., Lambert, C. G., & Gunawardhana, N. (2020). *Online Delivery of Teaching and Laboratory Practices: Continuity of University Programmes during COVID-19 Pandemic*. Educ. Sci. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci10100291>.

Readiness of Science Laboratory Facilities of the Public Junior High School in Lanao Del Sur, Philippines

Hadji Abas, H. T., & Marasigan, A. P. (2020). *Readiness of science laboratory facilities of the public junior high school in Lanao Del Sur, Philippines*. Retrieved on November 5, 2021 from <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3606078>.

Attitude and Cognitive Achievement in VLab Experience of STEM Learners in Chemistry

Larida, A., Disca, B., Olvis, P., & Docena, A. (2021). *Attitude and Cognitive Achievement in VLab Experience of STEM Learners in Chemistry*. International Journal of Sciences 58(2), 43-62.

Grade 12 STEM Students' Perceptions and Experiences In Home-Grown Chemistry Experiments

Pacifico, E., & Prudente, M. (n.d.). Grade 12 STEM students' perceptions and experiences in home-grown chemistry experiments. Retrieved November 17, 2021, from Edu.ph website: <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/pdf/conferences/research-congress-proceedings/2021/LLI-29.pdf>

Effectiveness of Virtual Laboratories in Science Education: A Meta-Analysis

Santos, M. L., & Prudente, M. (2021). *Effectiveness of virtual laboratories in science education: A meta-analysis*. Retrieved November 7, 2021, from Ijiet.org website: <http://www.ijiet.org/online/IJMET-3079.pdf>.